

Bioprotective Potential of Lactic Acid Bacteria and Food-Relevant Yeasts Against *Bacillus* spp. in Plant-Based Foods

Master Thesis (30 ECTS)

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Abstract

Plant-based foods are susceptible to spoilage by *Bacillus* spp., creating a need for natural biopreservation strategies compatible with minimally processed, clean-label products. Lactic acid bacteria and food-related yeast species are promising candidates for bioprotection in plant-based food matrices. However, knowledge on their interactions with *Bacillus* spp., particularly involving food-relevant yeasts and within plant-based systems, remains limited. This study evaluated the inhibitory potential of *Lactococcus lactis* and eight food-relevant yeast species against *Bacillus* spp. (*B. subtilis*, and *B. licheniformis*) using agar-based screening assays and co-culture fermentations in a plant-based food matrix. To investigate potential inhibitory mechanisms, acidification, organic acid production, and the susceptibility of *Bacillus* spp. to pH, organic acids, and nisin were assessed.

The results demonstrated species- and strain-specific variability in both inhibition and susceptibility. *Lc. lactis*, *Wickerhamomyces anomalus* and *Kluyveromyces marxianus* exhibited the strongest inhibitory activity in screening assays. *W. anomalus* achieved the lowest pH (~4.23), whereas *Lc. lactis* produced the highest total organic acid concentration (~3.2 g/L). Growth inhibition occurred at pH ≤ 4.2 , although viable cells remained detectable. Among the tested organic acids, propionic, acetic and formic acid caused complete loss of viability at ≥ 50 mM, while lactic and citric acid were less effective. Nisin prevented growth at ≥ 12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, although viable cells remained detectable. Co-culture fermentations indicated inhibition of *Bacillus* spp. by *Lc. lactis*, whereas yeast species showed limited inhibitory effects under tested conditions. The observed inhibition could not be solely attributed to acidification or organic acid production, indicating the involvement of additional antimicrobial mechanisms.

Overall, these findings support the potential use of *Lc. lactis* as a bioprotective culture in plant-based food systems. In contrast, the role of yeasts remains less clear and requires further investigation.

Resumé

Plantebaserede fødevarer er udsatte for fordærv forårsaget af *Bacillus* spp. hvilket skaber et behov for naturlige biokonserverings strategier, der er kompatible med minimalt forarbejdet clean-label produkter. Mælkesyrebakterier og fødevarerrelaterede gærarter er lovende kandidater til biobeskyttelse af plantebaserede fødevarer, men viden om deres interaktioner med *Bacillus* spp. er begrænset, særligt for fødevarerrelaterede gærarter og i plantebaserede matricer. Dette speciale undersøgte derfor det hæmmende potentiale af *Lactococcus lactis* og otte udvalgte fødevarerrelaterede gærarter mod *Bacillus* spp. (*B. subtilis* og *B. licheniformis*) ved hjælp af agar baserede screeningassays og co-culture fermentering i en plantebaseret fødevarematrix. For at undersøge potentielle hæmningsmekanismer, blev forsuring, produktion af organiske syrer, samt *Bacillus* spp. følsomhed overfor pH-, organiske syrer- og nisin undersøgt.

Resultaterne viste en arts- og stammeafhængig variation i både hæmning og overfølsomhed. *Lc. lactis*, *Wickerhamomyces anomalus* og *Kluyveromyces marxianus* udviste den stærkeste hæmmende aktivitet i screeningassays. *W. anomalus* opnåede den laveste pH-værdi (~4,23), mens *Lc. lactis* producerede den højeste samlede koncentration af organiske syrer (~3,2 g/L). Væksthæmning af *Bacillus* spp. var observeret ved $\text{pH} \leq 4,2$, dog med levedygtige celler observeret. Blandt de organiske syrer var propionsyre, eddikesyre og myresyre de mest hæmmende, med ingen overlevelse af *Bacillus* spp. ≥ 50 mM, mens mælkesyre og citronsyre var mindre effektive. Nisin medførte væksthæmning ved ≥ 12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, selvom levedygtige celler var observeret. Co-culture forsøg indikerede hæmning af *Bacillus* spp. af *Lc. lactis*, mens udvalgte gærarter viste begrænset hæmmende effekt under de testede forhold. Den observerede hæmning kunne ikke udelukkende tildeles forsuring eller produktion af organiske syrer, hvilket indikerer yderligere antimikrobielle mekanismer har været involveret.

Samlet set understøtter resultaterne potentialet for anvendelse af *Lc. lactis* som biobeskyttende kultur i plantebaserede fødevarer. Derimod, er gærarternes rolle fortsat uafklaret og kræver yderligere undersøgelser.

Preface

This Master thesis covers 30 ECTS points as part of the master's degree in Dairy Science and Technology at University of Copenhagen. The experimental work conducted in connection with this project was carried out in the Food Microbiology, Gut Health, and Fermentation section at the Department of Food science, from February to May 2026.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Plant-based Foods: Growth, Composition and Microbial Challenges

Plant-based foods represent a rapidly expanding segment of the global food industry, driven by increasing consumer awareness of health, sustainability, environmental implications, and ethical concerns regarding animal welfare (Tachie et al., 2023).

The growth is reflected in the European market, where plant-based retail sales increased by 21% between 2020 and 2022 across 13 European countries (Good Food Institute Europe, 2023). Within this market, plant-based meat products account for approximately 6% of the pre-packaged meat category, while plant-based milks represent approximately 11% of total milk sales (Good Food Institute Europe, 2023).

Plant-based foods are formulated from diverse raw materials such as legumes, peas, grains, and nuts (McClements & Grossmann, 2021), yet many share physicochemical characteristics relevant for microbial stability. These include relatively high moisture content, elevated water activity and near-neutral pH levels, conditions that support microbial growth (Mehta et al., 2025).

It has been demonstrated that spoilage microorganisms, including spore-forming bacteria, can grow as effectively in plant-based beverages as in dairy milk despite lower nutrient concentrations (Bartula et al., 2023).

Microbial contamination in plant-based foods may originate from raw materials, processing environments or storage conditions, leading to both spoilage and food safety concerns (Jing Jin et al., 2025). Among the microbial groups of concern, spore-forming bacteria represent a particular challenge due to their ability to survive heat treatments and persist throughout processing (Gleissle et al., 2025). Within this group, *Bacillus* spp. are especially relevant as spoilage microorganisms in plant-based food systems because they are abundant in plant-derived raw materials (Kyrylenko et al., 2023) and are environmentally resilient (Jenson, 2014).

1.2 *Bacillus* spp. and its Relevance to Food Safety and Spoilage

1.2.1 Taxonomy and General Characteristics

The genus *Bacillus* belongs to the phylum Firmicutes and the order Bacillales, and the family Bacillaceae, containing a diverse group of bacteria relevant to food spoilage and safety. Members of this genus are Gram-positive, rod-shaped bacteria, capable of forming highly resistant endospores. They are generally aerobic, although some species are facultative anaerobes (Gupta et al., 2020; Jenson, 2014).

Taxonomically, *Bacillus* is diverse and is commonly divided into the *Subtilis* clade and the *Cereus* clade. The *Subtilis* clade, include species such as *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus licheniformis*, and are generally regarded as non-pathogenic, however, frequently associated with food spoilage (Jenson, 2014; Kyrylenko et al., 2023; Vos et al., 2009). In contrast, the *Cereus* clade include well-known pathogenic species such as *Bacillus cereus* and *Bacillus anthracis* (Gupta et al., 2020), with *B. cereus* of particular importance in food systems due to its ability to cause human illness (Jenson, 2014).

These species exhibit broad physiological tolerance, but most species grow optimally between 25°C and 40°C. Although the majority are mesophilic, both psychrotolerant and thermophilic species have been reported (Vos et al., 2009). *B. subtilis* grows across a temperature range of 5-55°C (optimally at 28-30°C) and typically at a pH range of 5.5-8.5, whereas, *B. licheniformis* grows approximately between 15-55°C and at pH values above 4.2 and within a narrower typical range of 5.7-6.8 (Bautista, 2014; Vos et al., 2009), and tolerates relatively low water activity, with growth reported at a_w values as low as 0.90 (Yeak et al., 2022).

1.2.2 Occurrence in Food and Plant-based Matrices

The prevalence of *Bacillus* spp. makes them a major contributor to spoilage in plant-based food systems. *Bacillus* spp. are widely distributed in the environment and commonly enter the food chain through direct contact from soil to plant during cultivation and harvesting, making them frequent contaminants of plant-derived raw materials (Carlin, 2011; Kyrylenko et al., 2023).

They are often detected in starchy foods such as rice, cereals, potatoes, wheat flour, with reported detection rates up to 96% (Fangio et al., 2010), as well as in herbs spices and other dry plant

ingredients (Kyrylenko et al., 2023). Recent studies on oat, pea, almond and rice-based raw materials, show that *Bacillus* spp. often dominate the microbial community, with *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* among the most prevalent species (Gleissle et al., 2025; Kyrylenko et al., 2023).

The extent of microbial growth and spoilage in food products depends on the initial microbial load of the raw materials, intrinsic factors such as pH, a_w , and nutrient availability, as well as extrinsic factors including processing and storage conditions. As a result, microbial populations vary considerably between products, with some originating from the raw materials, while others may be introduced during production and handling (Mehta et al., 2025).

1.2.3 Spore Formation and Resistance

A defining characteristic of *Bacillus* spp. is their ability to form endospores, which are metabolically dormant, highly resistant structures produced within the bacterial cell in response to environmental stress such as nutrient limitation, pH changes, temperature shifts and population density (Jenson, 2014; Vos et al., 2009). Sporulation begins with an asymmetric cell division, producing a smaller forespore and a larger mother cell. The forespore is subsequently engulfed by the mother cell and develops into a mature endospore. Ultimately, the mother cell lyses, releasing the mature spore into the environment (Jenson, 2014).

Endospores possess a multilayered protective structure, including a cortex composed of modified peptidoglycan and a protein-rich spore coat, surrounding a highly dehydrated core. These features, combined with metabolic dormancy, results in a high level of resistance to environmental stresses, including heat, desiccation, radiation and chemical agents (Jenson, 2014; Vos et al., 2009) As a result, spores can persist for extended periods in food processing environments and survive conditions that inactivate vegetative cells (Gleissle et al., 2025; Ulrich, 2018).

In plant-based foods, the presence of *Bacillus* spores is particularly problematic, because raw plant materials often carry high initial spore loads. Kyrylenko et al. (2023) reported in 63% of examined plant ingredients, mesophilic spore counts were within 1 Log_{10} unit of total viable counts, with *B. licheniformis* and *B. subtilis* dominating the spore population.

1.2.4 Biofilm formation

In addition to spore formation, *Bacillus* spp. can establish robust biofilms on a wide range of food-contact surfaces such as stainless-steel equipment, rubber seals, conveyor belts and other industrial equipment (Faille et al., 2014; Kumar & Anand, 1998). This biofilm act as persistent reservoir of contamination, enabling cell transfer into food products during processing (Pérez-Rodríguez et al., 2008).

Biofilms consist of bacterial cells embedded within an extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) matrix, which creates a hydrated and highly structured environment (H-C & Wingender, 2001), providing stability and enhanced tolerance to cleaning agents and environmental stress (Chmielewski & Frank, 2003; Faille et al., 2014). Biofilms also facilitate cell-to-cell communication and genetic exchange (Haque et al., 2021), thereby promoting bacterial adaption, enhanced resistance to environmental stress factors and antimicrobials, and transfer of virulence traits (Michaelis & Grohmann, 2023).

Biofilm formation is influenced by both environmental conditions and strain-specific properties, resulting in variability in the ability of different *Bacillus* strains to persist in processing environments (Faille et al., 2014). Importantly, sporulation may occur within established biofilms, further contributing to long-term persistence and survival on food contact surfaces (Faille et al., 2014; Rahnama et al., 2023; Vos et al., 2009).

1.2.5 Foodborne Illness Associated with *Bacillus* Species

The majority of *Bacillus* spp. have limited pathogenic potential and are rarely associated with human disease, but *Bacillus cereus* is an well-established cause of foodborne illness (Vos et al., 2009) and remains one of the major contributors to outbreaks, including foods of non- animal origin. European Food Safety Authority data shows that *Bacillus* toxins accounted for approximately 14% of such outbreaks between 2020 and 2024 (EFSA, 2026).

Food poisoning caused by *B. cereus* appears as either an emetic or diarrhoeal syndrome. The emetic form is caused by cereulide, a heat- and acid-stable toxin pre-formed in food and are therefore capable of surviving both cooking and gastric passage (Batt, 2014). The diarrhoeal syndrome, on the other hand, is linked to heat-labile enterotoxins, including hemolysin BL (HBL), non-hemolytic

enterotoxin (NHE) and cytotoxin K (cytK), which are produced in the small intestine following ingestion of viable cells or spores (Batt, 2014).

Although *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* are generally considered non-pathogenic, they have occasionally been implicated in foodborne illness (Logan, 2012; Nieminen et al., 2007; Rønning et al., 2015; Salkinoja-Salonen et al., 1999). *B. licheniformis* can produce the surfactant lichenysin, which has been associated with gastrointestinal symptoms when present at sufficiently high levels (Yeak et al., 2022). Similarly, *B. subtilis* has been involved in rare cases of food poisoning, including those involving heat-stable toxins such as amyloisin (Logan, 2012). Despite these reports, illness caused by these species remain relatively uncommon than those attributed to *B. cereus* (Logan, 2012).

1.2.6 Role in Food Spoilage

Microbial spoilage is a major cause of quality loss in food products, driven by metabolic activities that negatively alter texture, flavour, odour and appearance (Gram et al., 2002). Among spoilage organisms, spore-forming *Bacillus* spp. are particularly problematic, due to their ability to survive processing through spore formation and subsequently germinate and grow in favourable environments (André et al., 2017; Franceschini et al., 2020).

Bacillus spp. produces a broad range of extracellular enzymes which degrades carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids in food products (Gleissle et al., 2025; Lorenzo et al., 2018).

Proteases degrade proteins into peptides and amino acids, which may subsequently be metabolised into ammonia and other nitrogenous compounds, causing pH increases and off flavours (Cirunay et al., 2026; Zhang et al., 2023). Lipases hydrolyse lipids, releasing free fatty acids associated with rancidity and undesirable flavours (Mafe et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2023), and amylases degrade starch into smaller carbohydrates, contributing to changes in texture and sweetness and providing fermentable carbohydrates for further metabolism (Jenson, 2014; Mafe et al., 2024). In carbohydrate rich foods, *Bacillus* spp. may ferment sugars and producing gas, off-flavours, and undesirable odours (Mafe et al., 2024)

Spoilage by *Bacillus* spp. is well documented in plant-based food products such as plant-protein ingredients (Champidou et al., 2024), soy foods (Shen et al., 2023), potatoes (Jenson, 2014), and cereal

based products (Dong et al., 2023), reflecting their ability to utilize diverse plant-derived substrates and thrive under the physicochemical conditions typical of these matrices (Vos et al., 2009). A well-documented example is the development of “ropy” bread, where spores survive baking, germinate, and produce extracellular polysaccharides and enzymes, causing a sticky, stringy texture, a discoloured crust and a characteristic melon-like odour (Kyrylenko et al., 2023; Pepe et al., 2003).

Overall, the extent and type of spoilage caused by *Bacillus* spp. depend on the interaction between microbial metabolic activity and the physicochemical properties of the food matrix (André et al., 2017).

1.2.7 Control Strategies and Limitations

Control of spore-forming *Bacillus* spp. in food systems relies on a combination of thermal, non-thermal and formulation-based strategies. (EFSA, 2016; Jing Jin et al., 2025; Kyrylenko et al., 2023). Heat treatment remains the primary method for microbial inactivation, but while pasteurization effectively eliminates vegetative cells, spores require sterilisation conditions that may compromise sensory and nutritional quality, as seen in plant-based beverages (Cho & Chung, 2020; EFSA, 2016). Refrigeration slows growth, making rapid cooling essential, but does not prevent proliferation of psychrotolerant *Bacillus* strains (EFSA, 2016).

Non-thermal technologies, such as high hydrostatic pressure can effectively reduce vegetative cells, but their efficacy against spores remains limited, and higher treatment intensities may negatively affect product quality (EFSA, 2016). Intrinsic factors such as pH and a_w can be adjusted to limit germination and growth, but such modifications may possibly not be wanted in plant-based foods due to impacts on sensory quality (Franceschini et al., 2020). Furthermore, chemicals can be used as preservatives, causing minimal changes to the fresh properties of food and guarantee microbiological food safety (Cho & Chung, 2020; Tenea et al., 2023). However, these can lead to several issues such as environmental pollution, as well as greater risks to human health due to chemical residues (Tenea et al., 2023).

These limitations, together with increasing demand for minimally processed and clean-label foods, highlight the need for alternative approaches that can inhibit *Bacillus* spp. without compromising product quality, providing the rationale for exploring biopreservation strategies in plant-based foods.

1.3 Biopreservation

Biopreservation has gained increasing attention as a natural preservation strategy in response to consumer demand for minimally processed, clean-label foods and the limitations of conventional preservation methods (Teshome, 2022). It involves the use of microorganisms and their metabolites to inhibit spoilage microorganisms and foodborne pathogens, thereby improving food quality and safety (Arbulu & Garcia-Gutierrez, 2024).

Biopreservation relies on the activity of protective cultures, which are live microorganisms intentionally added to food to inhibit undesirable microorganisms (Arbulu & Garcia-Gutierrez, 2024). Their antimicrobial effect typically arises from the production of antimicrobial metabolites such as organic acids, or the secretion of antimicrobial compounds such as bacteriocins, which may act individually or synergistically to inhibit competing microorganisms (Arbulu & Garcia-Gutierrez, 2024; Ramos et al., 2024; Teshome, 2022). To be effective, protective cultures must be safe, non-pathogenic, stable and metabolically active under the conditions of the food product, while maintaining sensory and nutritional quality (Arbulu & Garcia-Gutierrez, 2024; Ramos et al., 2024). Their performance is influenced by factors such as inoculation level, the native microbiota, and the food matrix (Ramos et al., 2024).

1.4 Lactic Acid Bacteria as Bioprotective Cultures

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are a diverse group of Gram-positive, non-spore-forming, aerotolerant anaerobic bacteria, characterized by their ability to ferment carbohydrates primarily into lactic acid (Vinderola et al., 2019). LAB have been widely used in food production in history, due to their technological and preservative properties and are Generally Recognised As Safe (GRAS-status) (Arbulu & Garcia-Gutierrez, 2024; Vinderola et al., 2024).

LAB are naturally associated with plant materials and are therefore well adapted to plant-based environments. Their ability to utilize plant-derived substrates and tolerate specific environmental conditions makes them promising protective cultures for plant-based foods (Fan et al., 2015).

Their preservative effect is primarily attributed to the production of a range of antimicrobial metabolites and other antimicrobial compounds that inhibit the growth of spoilage microorganisms. These include organic acids, bacteriocins and other secondary metabolites (Vinderola et al., 2024)

1.4.1 Fermentation pathways and Metabolite Production

The metabolite production of LAB depends on the fermentation pathways used. LAB obtain energy exclusively through substrate-level phosphorylation, due to the absence of a functional respiratory chain, and are broadly classified as homofermentative or heterofermentative based on their metabolic pathways (Vinderola et al., 2019). Homofermentative LAB metabolise hexoses through the Emden-Meyerhof-Parnas (EMP) pathway, producing lactic acid as the main end product and yielding two moles of ATP per mole of glucose. In contrast, heterofermentative LAB utilize the pentose phosphoketolase pathway, producing lactic acid along with carbon dioxide and either acetic acid or ethanol. The ATP yield varies depending on the end product. If ethanol is formed one mole of ATP is generated, and an extra ATP is generated if acetic acid is formed in the presence of alternative electron receptors (Vinderola et al., 2019).

1.4.2 Organic Acids Produced by LAB

Organic acids are antimicrobial metabolites produced by LAB, with lactic acid and acetic acid the most abundant. Additional acids, such as formic acid, may also be produced under aerobic conditions and under substrate limitation (Vinderola et al., 2024). The levels and types of organic acids produced depends on the species, culture composition and growth conditions (Özcelik et al., 2016).

Their inhibitory effect is mainly attributed to their ability to diffuse across bacterial cell membranes in their undissociated form. Once inside the cytoplasm, they dissociate, leading to intracellular acidification and accumulation of anions, lowering of the cell's internal pH, disrupting metabolic functions. The increased anion concentration can further induce osmotic imbalance, triggering potassium ion influx and glutamate efflux, resulting in growth inhibition (Arbulu & Garcia-Gutierrez, 2024; Vinderola et al., 2024). Additionally, acid stress may induce changes in membrane fatty acid composition, further impairing cell function (Vinderola et al., 2024).

It has also been reported that organic acids can induce specific stress responses. For example, exposure to lactic and acetic acid has been shown to alter gene expression in *B. cereus*, affecting

pathways related to amino acid catabolism, peptide transport systems and carbohydrate utilization. These findings indicate that the antimicrobial activity of organic acids also can involve complex physiological responses (Mols et al., 2010). In addition to intracellular effects, organic acids contribute to lowering the pH of the food matrix, creating an environment that is unfavourable for the growth of many spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms (Lund et al., 2020).

The antimicrobial activity of organic acids is highly pH-dependent and is greatest when acids are present in their undissociated form. The pH of the environment determines the ratio between dissociated and undissociated forms, determined by the acid dissociation constant (pKa). Therefore, organic acids are most effective at pH values near or below their pKa, where the proportion of undissociated acid is highest (van Beilen et al., 2016; Yoon, 2024).

In addition to organic acids, LAB may also produce other antimicrobial metabolites, such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and diacetyl. H_2O_2 is produced by LAB under aerobic conditions (Vinderola et al., 2024) and contributes to oxidative stress in susceptible microorganisms, damaging cellular components such as DNA, proteins and membrane lipids (Teshome, 2022; Vinderola et al., 2024). Diacetyl exhibits antimicrobial activity, particularly under acidic conditions (Vinderola et al., 2019). Although these metabolites typically occur at lower concentrations than organic acids, they may enhance overall antimicrobial activity in food systems (Vinderola et al., 2019).

1.4.3 Bacteriocins

Bacteriocins are ribosomally synthesized antimicrobial peptides produced LAB and other bacteria, exhibiting inhibitory activity against closely related species as well as a broader range of target microorganisms (Teshome, 2022; Vinderola et al., 2019). Among the most studied bacteriocins produced by LAB is nisin, produced by *Lactococcus lactis*, which is widely applied in the food industry, due to its effectiveness against foodborne pathogens such as *Listeria*, *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* species (Arbulu & Garcia-Gutierrez, 2024; Yi et al., 2022). Nisin belongs to the class I bacteriocins (lantibiotics), which are small heat-stable peptides that undergoes post-translational modification (Kumariya et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2025; Yi et al., 2022).

The antimicrobial activity of bacteriocins, combined with low toxicity and production by safe microorganisms, makes them more acceptable for health-conscious consumers (Vinderola et al., 2024). However, their efficacy is strongly influenced by environmental factors, such as pH and food

composition, and often most effective when used in combination with other preservation strategies (Ramos et al., 2024).

1.4.3.1 Mode of Action of Bacteriocins

Bacteriocins exert their antimicrobial activity primarily through disruption of the bacterial cell membrane. Nisin binds to lipid II, forming pores in the cytoplasmic membrane (Vinderola et al., 2019), leading to leakage of intracellular components, and collapse of the proton motive force, ultimately causing cell death. The proton motive force is critical for bacterial survival, as it drives ATP synthesis and facilitates the transport of solutes across the cell membrane (Kumariya et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2025; Yi et al., 2022).

In addition to membrane disruption, some bacteriocins may also inhibit essential cellular processes, including cell wall synthesis, DNA, RNA or protein synthesis, while others interfere with nutrient uptake or energy production through receptor-mediated interactions (Xu et al., 2025).

Although bacteriocins are effective, bacteria can develop resistance through mechanisms such as changes in membrane composition or modification of receptor molecules involved in the bacteriocin binding (Kumariya et al., 2019).

1.4.3.5 Bacteriocins produced by *Bacillus* spp.

Although bacteriocins are most commonly associated with LAB, several *Bacillus* spp. are also recognized as producers of antimicrobial peptides (Abriouel et al., 2011). Among the best characterized are subtilin produced by *B. subtilis* (Epparti et al., 2022), which shares structural and functional similarities with nisin (Caulier et al., 2019), including lipid II binding and pore formation (Abriouel et al., 2011; Epparti et al., 2022; Mercado & Olmos, 2022).

Bacteriocins and bacteriocin-like inhibitory substances produced by *Bacillus* spp. typically target Gram-positive bacteria, and in some cases yeasts, and are often highly stable across broad ranges of pH and temperature (Abriouel et al., 2011; Epparti et al., 2022). This highlights that *Bacillus* spp. can function not only as targets of antimicrobial activity, but also as active competitors capable of producing inhibitory compounds.

1.5 Bioprotective Potential of Food-relevant Yeasts

Yeasts are ubiquitous microorganisms found across a wide range of natural habitats. Their long history of use in biotechnology, particularly through the fermentative capacity of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, has traditionally focused on food and beverage production (Câmara & Sant'Ana, 2021; Kurtzman et al., 2011; Tenea et al., 2023). However, in recent decades, yeasts have gained increasing attention for their potential as bioprotective cultures due to their ability to inhibit spoilage microorganisms and foodborne pathogens through a range of mechanisms (Rima et al., 2012; Tenea et al., 2023).

1.5.1 Yeasts as Eukaryotic Microorganisms

Yeasts are eukaryotic unicellular fungi, characterised by the presence of a nucleus and membrane-bound subcellular organelles, distinguishing them from prokaryotic microorganisms (Baker et al., 2011). They reproduce asexual primarily through budding or fission, although many species also exhibit sexual reproduction (Kurtzman et al., 2011).

They are widespread in nature and are commonly found on plants, in soil, water and a variety of food products (Rima et al., 2012). They are particularly abundant in sugar-rich environments, such as fruit surfaces, plant exudates and fermented foods (Fadahunsi & Olubodun, 2021). In these environments, yeasts engage in diverse ecological interactions, including symbiosis, mutualism, parasitism, and competition with other microorganisms (Rima et al., 2012).

Most yeast species are mesophilic, with optimal growth typically between 20-30°C, although psychrophilic species may grow at 12-15°C and thermophilic yeasts above 24-30°C (Walker & Van Dijck, 2006). Growth typically occurs at pH 4.5-6.5, though some species tolerate more acidic or alkaline conditions. Yeasts require high water availability for growth and enzymatic activity, yet many species can grow at relatively low water activity (Walker & Van Dijck, 2006).

Yeasts energy metabolism is based on the oxidation of organic substrates, primarily carbohydrates, which serve as both carbon sources and energy yielding molecules for ATP production. While hexoses are preferred, many species can metabolize a wide range of carbon sources, including alcohols and organic acids (Rodrigues et al., 2006). Yeasts differ in their ability to ferment sugars and can be classified as non-fermentative, facultatively fermentative or obligately fermentative (Rima

et al., 2012). Non-fermentative rely exclusively on respiratory metabolism, in which glucose is converted to CO₂ and H₂O via glycolysis and the TCA cycle coupled with oxidative phosphorylation. In the TCA cycle, intermediate products such as citrate, malate and succinate can be formed. In contrast, obligate fermentative species primarily metabolize glucose through fermentation, resulting in ethanol and CO₂ as the main products. By-products such as glycerol, and smaller amounts of organic acids such as acetic acid can also be formed. Facultative fermentative species may display either a fully respiratory or a fermentative metabolism or both (Rodrigues et al., 2006).

1.5.2 Mechanisms of Yeast Mediated Microbial Inhibition

The antagonistic activity of yeasts against other microorganisms can be attributed to a variety of different properties, including competition for nutrients and space, alteration of pH in growth media, production of ethanol and the secretion and release of antimicrobial compounds. These compounds include volatile organic acids (VOCs), organic acids, hydrogen peroxide, extracellular enzymes, peptides and “killer toxins” (Mannazzu et al., 2019; Tenea et al., 2023).

1.5.2.1 Antimicrobial Peptides

Several yeast species produce antimicrobial peptides (Naimah et al., 2018). These low molecular weight peptides (Branco et al., 2015), exhibit broad antimicrobial activity against bacteria and fungi (Branco et al., 2015; Mirzaei et al., 2021). Their activity is generally mediated through interactions with the cell membrane, leading to membrane permeabilization, depolarization, leakage of cellular contents, resulting in cell death (Branco et al., 2015). In *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* small peptide fractions derived from glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) have been shown to exhibit antimicrobial activity by disrupting the plasma membrane of target cells and reducing intracellular pH (Branco et al., 2014; Mirzaei et al., 2021).

1.5.2.2 Killer Toxins

Yeasts produce a diverse range of extracellular killer toxins, characterised as glycoproteins or proteins, that inhibit susceptible microorganisms through a target-specific mode of action (Mannazzu et al., 2019). Killer-toxin-producing yeast strains were first described in *S. cerevisiae*, but have since been identified in several genera, including *Debaryomyces*, *Kluyveromyces*, *Pichia*, *Wickerhamomyces*, and *Candida* (Georgescu et al., 2024; He et al., 2024). These toxins enable yeasts

to suppress competing microorganisms and occupy ecological niches (El Dana et al., 2025). Well-characterized examples include the K1, K2, and K28 from *S. cerevisiae*, zymocin from *Kluyveromyces lactis*, PMKT/PMKT2 from *Pichia membranifaciens* and WaKT from *Wickerhamomyces anomalus* (Mannazzu et al., 2019).

Killer toxins are encoded by dsRNA virus-like particles (VLPs), circular or linear dsDNA virus-like elements (VLEs) or chromosomal genes (Mannazzu et al., 2019). Despite genetic differences, most killer toxins act through a two-step mechanism. First, the toxin binds to a primary receptor on the cell wall of susceptible cells, commonly β -1,3-D-glucans, β -1,6-D-glucans, mannoproteins or chitin (Mannazzu et al., 2019). This is followed by the interaction with a secondary receptor at the cell membrane, leading to toxin-specific killing mechanisms (Mannazzu et al., 2019). Some toxins form ion channels, causing leakage of K^+ , H^+ and ATP and other metabolites (Mannazzu et al., 2019), while other toxins interfere with cell cycle progression, leading to cell arrest in the G1/S phase (Klassen et al., 2017; Starmer & Lachance, 2011). Furthermore, certain toxins target cytoplasmic RNA, disrupting mRNA translation and protein synthesis, leading to cell lysis (Kast et al., 2014; Klassen et al., 2017; Uthman et al., 2011). Lastly, some toxins directly target the cell wall through enzymatic activity or inhibiting cell wall synthesis, leading to cell lysis (Klassen et al., 2017; Mannazzu et al., 2019).

The antimicrobial spectrum of killer toxins was initially thought to be restricted to closely related species and have mainly been studied for yeast-yeast antagonism in food and beverage systems (Freimoser et al., 2019). However, several killer toxins have since been shown to inhibit a broader range of microorganisms, including plant-pathogenic filamentous fungi (Freimoser et al., 2019; Mannazzu et al., 2019), and in some cases, bacteria. However, the antibacterial properties of yeast are much less documented than yeast-yeast antagonism (Muccilli & Restuccia, 2015).

1.5.3 Antagonistic Yeast Species with Biopreservation Potential

Although microbial antagonism in food systems has traditionally focused on LAB, increasing attention has been given to the antagonistic potential of naturally occurring yeasts (Muccilli & Restuccia, 2015). As summarized in Table 1, several yeast species have demonstrated inhibitory activity against plant pathogenic fungi, spoilage yeasts and foodborne bacteria, in vitro as well as across a variety of food matrices (He et al., 2024).

Table 1. Examples of antagonistic yeast species and strains, their target microorganisms in food matrices and in vitro and possible mechanism behind inhibition.

Yeast Species	Strain	Target Pathogen/ Spoilage microorganism	Mechanism	Food Types	References
<i>D. hansenii</i>	F9D	<i>P. expansum</i>	Cell wall lytic enzymes, nutrient competition, VOCs	Apple, pear	Arrarte et al. (2022)
	M13	<i>B. cinera</i> and <i>A. alternata</i> <i>Fusarium proliferatum</i>		Kiwifruit Musk melon	Sui et al. (2021) Rivas-Garcia et al. (2019)
	B9010	<i>Aspergillus sp.</i> , <i>B. fulva</i> , <i>B. nivea</i> , <i>Cladosporium sp.</i> , <i>Penicillium roqueforti</i> , <i>Penicillium candidum</i>		Cheese, yoghurt	Liu & Tsao (2009)
<i>K. lactis</i>	S-3-03	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.		In vitro	Ceugniesz et al. (2017)
<i>K. marxianus</i>	QKM-4	<i>Aspergillus spp.</i> ,	VOCs	Tomato, grape	Alasmar et al. (2020)
	WSYC 525	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> <i>E. coli</i>	Killer toxins	Cheese In vitro	Goerges et al. (2006) Chen et al. (2015)
	S-2-05	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.		In vitro	Ceugniesz et al. (2017)
<i>P. kudriazevii</i>	iwate20191107	<i>B. cereus</i>	VOCs	in vitro	Kanita & Jatmik (2023) Cabañas et al. (2020)
		<i>P. glabrum</i>		Grape	
<i>P. membranefaciens</i>	CYC 1106	<i>B. cinera</i>	Killer toxins	In vitro	Santos & Marquina (2004)
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>		<i>B. cinera</i> <i>A. carbonarius</i>	Competition for nutrients and space, VOCs	Grape Coffee fruit	Nally et al. (2012) Lino de Souza et al. (2021)
	RCAM 01730	<i>B. subtilis</i>		in vitro	Soboleva et al. (2016)
	RCAM 01731	<i>B. licheniformis</i> <i>E. coli</i>		in vitro in vitro	Soboleva et al. (2016) Chen et al (2015)
<i>S. occidentalis</i>	ATCC 44252	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	Killer toxin	In vitro	Chen et al. (2000)
<i>W. anomalus</i>	WRL-076	<i>A. flavus</i>		In vitro	Hua et al. (2019)
	CBS S605T	<i>B. subtilis</i>		In vitro	Novichenko et al. (2024)
		<i>B. cinera</i>		Tomato	Lanhuang et al. (2022)

Yeasts possess several traits that support their potential use as bioprotective cultures, including broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity, genetic stability, simple nutritional requirements, and the ability to grow under challenging environmental conditions, such as low temperatures, acidic pH, osmotic stress (He et al., 2024). Many species are also regarded as safe, with several species holding GRAS status (Rima et al., 2012). *W. anomalus* in particular has attracted interest due to its specific characteristics, adaption properties, its wide-spread occurrence in natural environments, and involvement in various fermentation processes (Giovati et al., 2021).

Although various yeast species exhibit antimicrobial activity, their efficacy is strongly influenced by several external factors, including the target microorganism, food matrix, and environmental

conditions such as nutrient availability, temperature, pH, and salt concentration. While optimal conditions differ between killer toxins, most killer toxins are active under slightly acidic conditions (pH 4.0-5.5) and at temperatures below 30°C (El Dana et al., 2025; Muccilli & Restuccia, 2015). Consequently, the antagonistic mechanisms of a given yeast strain may vary across applications, presenting a challenge in developing universal antagonistic yeast-based bioprotective cultures (Ma et al., 2023). Importantly, antimicrobial efficacy in food systems may differ from laboratory conditions, as interactions with food components and physicochemical properties such as pH, fat and protein content, and a_w can influence the antimicrobial activity (Kumar et al., 2025). This highlights the need for investigating antimicrobial effects by yeasts in real food matrices.

Despite extensive research on yeast antagonism in postharvest systems and spoilage control, their application as bioprotective cultures in processed foods remains limited, representing a promising direction for future research and development in biopreservation (He et al., 2024).

1.8 Research Objectives

The overall aim of this project was to investigate the bioprotective potential of *Lactococcus lactis* and selected food-relevant yeast species against *Bacillus* spp. in plant-based food matrices, and to identify potential mechanisms responsible for microbial inhibition.

The specific objectives of this study were to (i) screen selected lactic acid bacteria and yeast strains for inhibitory activity against *Bacillus* spp., (ii) determine the tolerance of *Bacillus* spp. to pH, organic acid and nisin (iii) evaluate acidification capacity and organic acid production of *Lc. lactis* and selected yeast species in relation to inhibitory thresholds of *Bacillus* spp., and (iv) assess inhibitory activity in a plant-based matrix using co-culture experiments.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Selected Microorganisms

The microorganisms used in this study comprised one lactic acid bacteria, eight yeast strains, and five *Bacillus* strains. Microorganisms used and their isolation source are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Microorganisms obtained from different food relevant sources

Genus	Species	Strain	Isolation source
<i>Bacillus</i> spp.			
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Subtilis</i> var. Natto		Fava beans
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Subtilis</i>	Fb1	Fava beans
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Licheniformis</i>	Fb2	Fava beans
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Licheniformis</i>	Fb3	Fava beans
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Subtilis</i>	Fb4	Fava beans
Lactic acid bacteria			
<i>Lactococcus</i>	<i>Lactis</i>	NcimB702091	Seeds of Chinese radish from Japan
Yeasts			
<i>Debaryomyces</i>	<i>hansenii</i>	MD 02	Mejeri isolater 1999
<i>Kluyveromyces</i>	<i>lactis</i>	SP19#10	White-brined cheese with sundried tomatoes
<i>Kluyveromyces</i>	<i>marxianus</i>	TSL3	Skyr isolates - Thise sample
<i>Pichia</i>	<i>kudriavzevii</i>	36h3c2	mawè, Benin
<i>Pichia</i>	<i>membranefaciens</i>	PM6-21	Cacao
<i>Saccharomyces</i>	<i>cerevisiae</i>	18-28	Nunu
<i>Schwanniomyces</i>	<i>occidentalis</i>	DSM3794	soil, Spain
<i>Wickerhamomyces</i>	<i>anomalous</i>	SP17#2	White-brined cheese with sundried tomatoes

2.2 Growth media and Culture conditions

MYGP broth for yeast cultivation was prepared by dissolving 10 g/L D(+) Glucose (Merck, Germany), 5 g/L Bacto peptone (HiMedia Laboratories, India), 3/L g yeast extract (Gibco, USA), and 3/L g malt extract (EO Laboratories, UK) in deionised water. Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) broth for the cultivation of *Bacillus* spp. was prepared by dissolving 37 g/L BHI powder (Biokar Diagnostics, France) in deionised water. GM17 broth for *Lc. Lactis* was prepared by dissolving 42 g/L M17 broth (Liofilchem, Italy) and 5 g/L D(+) Glucose (Merck, Germany) in deionised water. All media were autoclaved at 121°C for 20 min. Solid media were prepared by the addition of 20 g/L agar prior to autoclaving. After sterilisation, the media were cooled to approximately 55°C and poured aseptically into sterile petri dishes.

All strains were collected from a freezer (-80°C), and for routine use, streaked onto appropriate agar plates with an inoculation loop. Yeasts were incubated at 25°C for 48 hours, while *Bacillus* spp. and *Lc. lactis* were incubated at 30°C for 24 hours. Plates were stored at 4°C. Additionally, new stocks of each strain were prepared by mixing 500 uL of 40% glycerol (86%, VWR chemicals, USA) with 500 uL ON-culture in cryotubes and stored at -60°C. These stocks were used to periodically refresh working cultures.

Overnight cultures (ON-cultures) were prepared by inoculating a single colony into 10 mL of appropriate liquid broth, followed by vortexing and incubation at 25°C (yeasts) or 30°C (*Bacillus* spp. and *Lc. lactis*) with shaking (190 rpm) for approximately 20 hours.

2.3 Screening of *Lc. lactis* and Food-Related yeasts for Inhibitory Activity

To evaluate potential inhibitory interactions between *Lc. Lactis*, yeasts and *Bacillus* spp., a spot assay with soft agar overlay was used, allowing diffusion-based detection of antimicrobial effects. The optical density (OD₆₀₀) of *Lc. lactis* and yeast ON-cultures was measured using a spectrophotometer (GENESYS 180 UV-Visible spectrophotometer, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) to standardize cultures to comparable cell densities (~10⁷ CFU/mL). Subsequently, 3 uL of each culture was spotted onto GM17 agar (*Lc. lactis*) or MYGP agar (yeasts) and incubated for 24 hours at 30°C and 25°C, respectively, to allow colony establishment prior to overlay.

Soft agar was prepared by supplementing BHI broth with 0.7% agar, followed by autoclaving. The OD₆₀₀ of *Bacillus* cultures was measured, and inoculum volumes were calculated to achieve approximately 10⁵ CFU/mL in the soft agar. The inoculated soft agar was cooled to approximately 45°C and poured onto the plates containing *Lc. lactis* or yeast colonies. After solidification, plates were incubated at 30°C for 17 hours, after which inhibition zones were evaluated qualitatively based on the presence of clear zones surrounding colonies, as well as quantitative by measuring the diameter (mm) of the clear area surrounding each spotted colony. Measurements were performed in duplicate and reported as mean inhibition zone diameter \pm SD.

2.4 pH Measurements of *Lc. lactis* and Food Related Yeasts

To assess the ability of the microorganisms to acidify their environment, pH development was monitored over time. 1 mL of ON-culture with *Lc. lactis* and each yeast strain were inoculated into 9 mL of GM17 broth or MYGP broth in sterile culture tubes and incubated at, respectively, 30°C and 25°C with shaking at 190 rpm. Cultures were prepared for four incubation times (24 h, 48 h, 1 week, and 2 weeks). At each time point, pH was measured using a calibrated pH meter (PHM250 Ion Analyser, Radiometer Analytical, France). Triplicates were made.

2.5 High-Performance Liquid Chromatography on *Lc. lactis* and Food Related Yeasts

To quantify organic acid production as a potential mechanism of inhibition, culture supernatants were analysed by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC).

From each ON-culture, 5 ml of *Lc. lactis* and yeast strains were pipetted into 15 ml sterile falcon tubes. Subsequently, 2.5 ml of 0.1 M potassium ferrocyanide (Merck, Germany) and 2.5 ml of 0.2 M zinc sulfate (Merck, Germany) prepared in autoclaved Mili-Q water, were added for protein precipitation. Samples were mixed gently by inversion and centrifuged at 4400 rfc for 30 min. The supernatant was collected using 10 mL syringes and filtered through a 0.22 μ m membrane filter (Millex™ syringe filter, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) into new 15 ml falcon tubes, followed by storage at -18°C until analysis. Prior to HPLC analysis, samples were thawed, and 1 ml was pipetted into HPLC vials. Calibration standards (0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 g/L) were prepared for citric, lactic, formic, acetic, and propionic acid. Samples were analyzed using an HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, USA), equipped with a 1200 series pump, and 1100 series autosampler and a 1260 Infinity II refractive index

detector (RID). Chromatographic separation was performed on an Aminex HPX-87H column (300 x 7.8 mm, Bio-Rad, Hercules, USA) maintained at 35°C. samples were injected at a volume of 20 μ L and eluted using 5 mM sulfuric acid in Mili-Q water as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min, with a total runtime of 30 min.

2.6 Determination of The Effect of pH on Growth of *Bacillus* spp.

To determine the influence of pH on *Bacillus* growth, BHI broth was adjusted to pH values of 3.5, 4, 4.2, 4.4, 4.6, 4.8, 5.0 and 7.0 using 1 mol/L sodium hydroxide (VWR chemicals, USA) and 1 mol/L hydrochloric acid (VWR chemicals, USA) followed by autoclavation. Subcultures were prepared by inoculating 1 mL of ON-cultures into 9 mL fresh BHI broth and incubating at 30°C (190 rpm) until $OD_{600} \approx 0.2-0.3$ to reach early exponential phase. A 96-well microtiter plate was sterilized by being exposed to UV light for 25 min prior to use. Each well was inoculated with 20 μ L subculture and 180 μ L pH adjusted medium, mixed by pipetting up and down a few times, and sealed with an adhesive breathable film (Z380059, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany). Duplicates were prepared. Growth was monitored using a plate reader (Multiskan FC, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) measuring OD_{600} every hour for 48 hours at 30°C with moderate shaking. Duplicates were made.

Additionally, 10-fold serial dilutions (10^{-1} - 10^{-7}) were performed, and 100 μ L of the appropriate dilutions were spread-plated onto BHI agar using a sterile Drigalski spatula for CFU determination at 48 hours. These plates were incubated at 30°C for 24 hours. Plates containing 30-300 colonies were used for enumeration. In parallel, pH measurements were conducted after 48 hours of incubation (30°C, 190 rpm) in separate tubes containing 9 mL BHI broth and 1 mL subculture to monitor any pH changes during growth. Duplicates were made.

2.7 Antimicrobial Effect of Organic Acids on *Bacillus* spp.

To evaluate the antimicrobial effects of individual organic acids independently of pH, defined acid concentrations were tested at a constant pH of 5.0. Stock solutions (1 M) of lactic (80%, Bie&Berntsen, Denmark), acetic (100%, Merck, Germany), propionic ($\geq 99\%$, Merck, Germany), formic (85%, Bie&Berntsen, Denmark), and citric acid ($\geq 99\%$, Merck, Germany), were prepared and subsequently diluted in BHI broth to reach final concentrations of 0, 10, 25, 50, and 100 mM. These solutions were adjusted to pH 5.0 using 1 mol/l Sodium hydroxide (VWR chemicals, USA) and 1 mol/l Hydrochloric acid (VWR chemicals, USA) before being sterilized by autoclaving.

To ensure the use of cells in the early exponential phase, a subculture of *Bacillus licheniformis* Fb2 was prepared. Prior to inoculation, a 96-well microtiter plate was sterilized via UV light exposure for 25 minutes. Each well was inoculated with 20 uL of subculture and 180 uL of the respective medium, mixed by pipetting, and sealed with an adhesive breathable film (Z380059, Sigma-Aldrich, Merck, Germany) allowing air exchange. All experiments were performed in duplicate. Growth was monitored using a plate reader (Multiskan FC, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) measuring OD600 every hour for 48 hours at 30°C with moderate shaking.

Additionally, CFU and pH after 48 hours was determined, as described in section 2.6.

2.8 Antimicrobial Effect of Nisin on *Bacillus* spp.

To assess the antimicrobial effects of nisin on *Bacillus* spp., seven different concentrations were tested on *B. subtilis* var. natto, *B. subtilis* Fb1 and *B. licheniformis* Fb2. Stock solution of 10 mg/ml was made by adding 100 mg Nisin (≥ 900 IU/mg, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) to 10 ml Mili-Q water. This solution was passed through a 0.22 μm filter (Millex™ syringe filter, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) and subsequently diluted in BHI broth to reach concentrations of 0, 1.0, 3.0, 6.0, 12.5, 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ active nisin. To ensure the use of cells in the early exponential phase, subcultures of the three *Bacillus* strains was prepared. Prior to inoculation, a 96-well microtiter plate was sterilized via UV light exposure for 25 minutes. Each well was inoculated with 20 uL of subculture and 180 uL of the medium with respective concentrations of nisin, mixed by pipetting, and sealed with an adhesive breathable film (Z380059, Sigma-Aldrich, Merck, Germany). All experiments were performed in Triplicate. Growth was monitored using a plate reader (Multiskan FC, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) measuring OD600 every hour for 48 hours at 30°C with moderate shaking.

Additionally, CFU and pH after 48 hours was determined, as described in section 2.6.

2.9 Growth and inhibition of *Bacillus* in Plant-Based Matrix

To assess microbial interactions within a plant-based food matrix, 200 g of sterilized dry fava beans were soaked in 400 ml of sterile Mili-Q water for 17 hours at 4°C in a sterile 1 L blue cap bottle. Following the soaking period, excess water was removed by passing it through a sterile plastic funnel lined with a sterile cloth. Samples consisting of 7 g of soaked beans each were then transferred to sterile petri dishes.

For the LAB and yeasts treatments, 5 ml ON-cultures of *Lc. lactis*, *W. anomalus* and *K. marxianus* ($\sim 10^7$ CFU/ml) were centrifuged for 10 minutes at 4400 rfc at 4°C in 15 ml falcon tubes. The resulting supernatants were discarded, and the pellets were resuspended in 0.9% NaCl water. A 500 μ L volume of the washed yeast cells in saline water suspension was inoculated onto the beans and mixed using a sterile spoon to ensure uniform coverage. Fava beans were first inoculated with LAB or yeast for 24 hours at 30°C or 25°C, respectively, prior to inoculation with *B. licheniformis* Fb2. Triplicates were made.

Preparation of the *B. licheniformis* Fb2 inoculum involved transferring a 10%(v/v) ON-culture into 9 mL of fresh BHI broth, followed by the incubation at 30°C (190 rpm) until an OD600 of 0.2-0.3 to ensure early-exponential phase. 5 ml of this subculture was centrifuged in 15 ml falcon tubes (10 min, 4400 rfc, 4°C), and the pellet was washed and resuspended in 0.9% NaCl. The culture was then adjusted to three different inoculum levels (10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4 CFU/mL). A 500 μ L volume of each inoculum level was applied to both the LAB and yeast-pretreated beans and as well as untreated fava bean controls. The samples and controls were subsequently incubated for 24 hours at 30°C. Triplicates were made. Following incubation, approximately 2.5 g of beans from each sample was transferred to a stomacher bag with a 1:10 ratio of sterile Mili-Q water. The samples were processed in a stomacher (Stomacher 80, Seward, UK) for 60 seconds at normal speed. 1 mL of the resulting suspension (10^{-1} dilution) was used to prepare a 10-fold serial dilution series up to 10^{-7} . 100 μ L of appropriate dilutions were spread-plated onto BHI agar using a sterile Drigalski spatula and incubated for 24 hours at 30°C for the final CFU determination of *B. licheniformis* Fb2.

2.10 Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed in PyCharm 2026.1. Mean values and standard deviations were calculated from duplicate (n=2) or triplicate (n=3) measurements, as specified for each experiment. Differences between experimental conditions were assessed using two-way ANOVA for pH measurements of *Lc. lactis* and food related yeasts, and one-way ANOVA for CFU and alkalization data in the experiments on inhibitory effects of pH, organic acids and nisin. ANOVA was followed by Tukey's post-hoc test for pairwise comparisons. Due to limited biological replication in some experiments (n=2), statistical power was considered limited and were interpreted alongside observed trends rather than strict significance testing alone. A significance threshold of $p < 0.05$ was applied.

3. Results

3.1 Screening of *Lc. lactis* and Food-Related yeasts for Inhibitory Activity

Initial screening using spot assays was performed to evaluate the inhibitory potential of *Lactococcus lactis* and food-related yeast species against five *Bacillus* indicator strains. Examples for *Lc. lactis* and two yeast species (*Wickerhamomyces anomalus* and *Kluyveromyces marxianus*) are shown in **Figure 1**, while full screening results are provided in Appendix A. Clear halos surrounding the inhibitor spots indicate inhibition of the respective *Bacillus* strains.

Figure 1: Screening of inhibitory activity of *Lc. lactis* and selected yeast species against five *Bacillus* strains. The figure illustrates the examples of interactions between inhibitor spots (centre) and a lawn of indication strains (*B. subtilis* var. Natto, *B. subtilis* Fb1, *B. licheniformis* Fb2 and *B. licheniformis* Fb3, *B. subtilis* Fb4). Clear halos surrounding the inhibitor spots indicates inhibitory activity against sensitive strain. Left: *K. marxianus* against *B. subtilis* var. Natto, middle: *W. anomalus* against *B. licheniformis* Fb2, right: *Lc. lactis* against *B. subtilis* var. Natto.

The screening revealed clear species-dependent differences in inhibitory activity. *W. anomalus* and *K. marxianus* exhibited the strongest inhibition among the yeasts, producing distinct and well-defined zones against all *Bacillus* strains. In contrast, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and the additional yeast species showed little or no detectable inhibition.

Lc. lactis showed a different inhibition pattern compared to the yeasts, forming irregular but generally pronounced clearing zones. Inhibition was observed against *Bacillus subtilis* var. Natto and *Bacillus licheniformis* (Fb2 and Fb3), whereas *B. subtilis* Fb1 and Fb4 was less affected.

Quantitative measurements of inhibition zones (Table 3) supported these observations. *W. anomalus* and *K. marxianus* were the only species capable of inhibiting all five *Bacillus* strains, although zone sizes varied considerably. *W. anomalus* produced the largest zones among the yeasts, including 8.5 ± 0.71 mm against *B. licheniformis* Fb2 and 9 ± 2.82 mm against *B. subtilis* Fb4. *Kluyveromyces lactis* showed limited inhibition, while *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Pichia kudriazevii*, *Pichia*

membranifaciens, and *Debaryomyces hansenii* showed no detectable inhibition under the experimental conditions.

Table 3: Quantitative assessment of the inhibitory activity of *Lc. lactis* and selected yeast species against five *Bacillus* strains. The values represent the mean area of the inhibition zones (mm) (colony diameter (mm) - Inhibition zone diameter (mm)) \pm SD of n=2. Columns represent the specific *Bacillus* strains (*B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis*), while rows list the species tested for their inhibitory potential. (-) indicates no visible zone of inhibition under the experimental conditions.

	Inhibition zone (mm)				
	<i>B. subtilis</i> var. Natto	<i>B. subtilis</i> Fb1	<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb2	<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb3	<i>B. subtilis</i> Fb4
<i>D. hansenii</i>	-	-	-	-	-
<i>K. lactis</i>	1.0 \pm 1.14	0.5 \pm 0.71	-	-	-
<i>K. marxianus</i>	2.5 \pm 3.54	1.0 \pm 1.14	3.0 \pm 4.24	1.0 \pm 1.41	3 \pm 4.24
<i>P.kudriavzevii</i>	-	-	-	-	-
<i>P.membranifaciens</i>	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. occidentalis</i>	-	-	-	-	-
<i>W. anomalus</i>	7.0 \pm 4.24	6.0 \pm 5.65	8.5 \pm 0.71	7.0 \pm 1.41	9 \pm 2.82
<i>Lc. lactis</i>	8.67 \pm 4.16	-	12.67 \pm 2.31	9.67 \pm 8.02	-

Among the indicator strains, *B. subtilis* var. Natto was generally the most susceptible, whereas *B. subtilis* Fb1 and Fb4 showed greater resistance. *B. licheniformis* Fb2 was particularly sensitive to *Lc. lactis*, which produced the largest inhibition zone in the study (12.67 \pm 2.31 mm).

Variability between replicates was observed for both *Lc. lactis* and the yeast species.

3.2 pH Measurements of *Lc. lactis* and Food-Related Yeast Species

The pH dynamics in GM17 broth inoculated with *Lc. lactis*, alongside MYGP broth inoculated with eight yeast species over 336 hours, are presented in **Figure 2**, with mean pH values \pm SD summarised in **Table 4**. As expected from the media composition, *Lc. lactis* started at a slightly higher initial pH (6.52 \pm 0.02) than the yeasts (6.16 \pm 0.06).

Figure 2: pH over 336 hours in GM17 broth inoculated with *Lc. lactis* and MYGP broth inoculated with eight food-related yeast species. Line plot showing temporal pH changes for all species. Line represents the mean of triplicate (n=3).

All microorganisms acidified the medium within the first 48 hours, after which species-dependent differences emerged. *P. kudriazevii* and *W. anomalus* showed the strongest and most sustained acidification, reaching minimum pH values of 4.50 ± 0.40 and 4.23 ± 0.11 , respectively, and maintaining low pH throughout the incubation period. *D. hansenii*, *K. lactis*, and *K. marxianus* exhibited more moderate acidifications, followed by gradual deacidification, with *K. marxianus* returning to near-neutral pH (5.90 ± 0.13) by 336 hours.

Intermediate behaviour was observed for *S. cerevisiae*, *P. membranifaciens* and *S. occidentalis*, which reached minimum pH levels between 4.56 and 4.76, before stabilising or partially increasing pH. *Lc. lactis* showed a rapid initial decrease to 5.36 ± 0.03 within 24 hours, after which pH remained stable throughout the remaining incubation period.

Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences between species over time ($p < 0.001$). Differences were minor during the initial 48 h but became increasingly significant at 168 hours and 336 hours, with *W. anomalus* and *P. kudriazevii* exhibiting significantly stronger acidification compared to other species.

Table 4: pH Mean values \pm SD of broth inoculated with *Lc. lactis* and Food Related Yeast Species. Values within the same row followed by different uppercase letters indicate significant differences between species at a specific time point ($p < 0.05$) according to Tukey's post-hoc test. Groups sharing the same letter are not significantly different, whereas groups with different letters indicate statistically significant differences. $n=3$.

	<i>D. hansenii</i>	<i>K. lactis</i>	<i>K. marxianus</i>	<i>P. kudriazevii</i>	<i>P. membranifaciens</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>S. occidentalis</i>	<i>W. anomalus</i>	<i>Lc. lactis</i>
0 h	6.16 \pm 0.06 ^a	6.16 \pm 0.06 ^{ab}	6.16 \pm 0.06 ^{ac}	6.16 \pm 0.06 ^{ae}	6.16 \pm 0.06 ^{af}	6.16 \pm 0.06 ^{ag}	6.16 \pm 0.06 ^{ah}	6.16 \pm 0.06 ^{ai}	6.16 \pm 0.02 ^d
24 h	5.77 \pm 0.08 ^a	5.50 \pm 0.15 ^{ab}	5.28 \pm 0.30 ^{ac}	4.75 \pm 0.16 ^e	5.48 \pm 0.21 ^{af}	5.21 \pm 0.33 ^{ag}	4.99 \pm 0.09 ^h	5.09 \pm 0.55 ^{ai}	5.36 \pm 0.03 ^{ad}
48 h	5.09 \pm 0.41 ^a	4.78 \pm 0.17 ^{ab}	5.11 \pm 0.90 ^{ac}	4.57 \pm 0.23 ^{ae}	4.64 \pm 0.32 ^{af}	4.69 \pm 0.06 ^{ag}	4.80 \pm 0.10 ^{ah}	4.56 \pm 0.17 ^{ai}	5.28 \pm 0.03 ^{ad}
168 h	5.25 \pm 0.12 ^a	5.02 \pm 0.02 ^{ab}	4.84 \pm 0.40 ^{ac}	4.49 \pm 0.40 ^e	4.88 \pm 0.27 ^{af}	4.56 \pm 0.11 ^g	4.76 \pm 0.42 ^{ah}	4.23 \pm 0.11 ⁱ	5.37 \pm 0.02 ^{ad}
336 h	5.75 \pm 0.11 ^a	5.76 \pm 0.18 ^{ab}	5.90 \pm 0.13 ^{ac}	4.65 \pm 0.06 ^e	4.72 \pm 0.12 ^{ef}	4.89 \pm 0.14 ^{eg}	5.54 \pm 0.29 ^{ah}	4.31 \pm 0.02 ⁱ	5.36 \pm 0.02 ^d

3.3 Determination of The Effect of pH on Growth of *Bacillus* spp.

The growth kinetics of five *Bacillus* strains were evaluated across a pH gradient (3.5-7.0) to determine their acid tolerance and growth thresholds (**Figure 3**). pH strongly influenced both lag phase duration and maximum biomass yield.

Growth was completely inhibited at pH 3.5-4.0 in all strains. Limited strain-dependent growth emerged at pH 4.2, where *B. subtilis* strains (var. Natto, Fb1 and Fb4) showed detectable increases in OD600, whereas *B. licheniformis* (Fb2 and Fb3) remained largely inhibited.

Between pH 4.4 and 5.0, growth progressively improved, although acid stress prolonged lag phases. For example, *B. licheniformis* Fb2, showed 19 hours delay in exponential growth at pH 4.4 compared to pH 7.0. At this pH level, no growth was observed for *B. licheniformis* Fb3.

Figure 3: Growth curves of five *Bacillus* strains across eight pH conditions. The figure consists of a subplot with five individual line plots, each representing a bacterial strain. Growth was measured over time under eight different pH conditions, with each line within the plots corresponding to a specific pH value. Curves are based on mean values of duplicates (n=2). Single measurements include *B. subtilis* var. natto at pH 4.6 and 4.8, *B. subtilis* Fb1 at pH 4.2 and 4.4, *B. licheniformis* Fb2 at pH 4.4, *B. licheniformis* Fb3 at pH 4.6 and *B. subtilis* Fb4 at pH 5.0 and 7.0.

Viable cell counts (\log_{10} CFU/mL) after 48 hours were measured to complement the growth kinetic data and assess survival at endpoint (**Figure 4**). These data supported the pH thresholds observed in the growth curves. Viability remained strongly reduced at pH 3.5-4.0. At pH 3.5, only *B. subtilis* Fb1, Fb4 and *B. licheniformis* Fb3 showed detectable viability, whereas viability increased slightly across strains at pH 4.0, although still significantly lower than at $\text{pH} \geq 4.4$.

Figure 4: Viable cell counts (\log_{10} CFU/ml) for selected *Bacillus* strains after 48 hours incubation across a pH gradient. The bars represent means of \log_{10} transformed Colony Forming Units (CFU) per ml for *B. subtilis* (var. Natto, Fb1 and Fb4) and *B. licheniformis* (Fb2 and Fb3). The error bars indicate the standard deviation (SD) based on n=2 independent replicates. Single measurements are shown at pH 4 for *B. subtilis* Fb1 and *B. licheniformis* Fb2, and at pH 4.8 for *B. licheniformis* Fb3. ND= no colonies detected

From pH 4.4 and above, all strains reached high final cell densities (7.6 -8.8 \log_{10} CFU/mL), and were not significantly different, this suggests that initial pH primarily affected the ability to establish growth rather than the final cell densities. Variability was highest at pH 4.4, particularly for *B. subtilis* var. Natto and *B. licheniformis* Fb3. Initial pH significantly affected growth and viability in all strains except var. Natto ($p < 0.05$), with post-hoc comparisons showing significant lower cell densities at pH 3.5-4.0 compared with ≥ 4.4 .

Changes in medium pH after 48 hours reflected strain metabolic activity under the different initial pH conditions (*Table 5*).

Table 5: De-acidification potential of five *Bacillus* strains across a pH gradient after 48 hours. The values represent the pH change after 48 hours incubation for strains of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* across an initial pH gradient. Data points represent the mean±SD of duplicates (n=2), except *B. subtilis* Fb4 at an initial pH of 4.6, which is a single measurement. Values within the same column followed by different uppercase letters indicate significant differences between strains at that specific initial pH (<0.05) according to Tukey's post-hoc test. Groups sharing the same letter are not significantly different, whereas groups with different letters indicate statistically significant differences.

	Initial pH							
	3.5	4.0	4.2	4.4	4.6	4.8	5.0	7.0
<i>B. subtilis</i> var. Natto	3.78±0.04 ^a	4.37±0.13 ^a	4.67±0.14 ^a	5.34±1.03 ^a	6.45±0.69 ^a	6.58±0.47 ^a	6.72±0.66 ^a	7.38±0.46 ^a
<i>B. subtilis</i> Fb1	3.78±0.04 ^a	4.49±0.11 ^a	6.09±0.08 ^b	6.48±0.06 ^b	6.7±0.26 ^b	6.93±0.36 ^b	7.04±0.45 ^b	7.53±0.54 ^a
<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb2	3.77±0.00 ^a	4.42±0.06 ^a	4.67±0.12 ^a	5.96±0.33 ^a	6.69±0.30 ^b	6.83±0.37 ^b	6.91±0.39 ^b	7.38±0.58 ^a
<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb3	3.79±0.02 ^a	4.42±0.05 ^a	4.62±0.09 ^a	5.66±1.08 ^a	6.77±0.23 ^b	6.98±0.41 ^b	6.92±0.26 ^a	7.49±0.51 ^a
<i>B. subtilis</i> Fb4	3.81±0.05 ^a	4.46±0.09 ^a	5.84±0.14 ^b	6.53±0.09 ^b	6.72 ^(b)	6.66±0.00 ^b	7.19±0.54 ^b	7.59±0.54 ^a

Minimal alkalization was observed at pH 3.5-4.0, suggesting strongly inhibited metabolism under highly acidic conditions. At pH 4.2-4.4, strain-dependent differences emerged, with *B. subtilis* Fb1 and Fb4 showing substantial alkalization, whereas *B. subtilis* var. Natto and the *B. licheniformis* strains (Fb2 and Fb3), exhibited weaker pH increases. From pH 4.6 and above, all strains substantially alkalized the medium, suggesting active metabolism under permissive conditions. However, only minor pH increases were observed at the control pH (7.0), despite robust growth across all strains.

3.4 High-Performance Liquid Chromatography on *Lc. lactis* and Food-Relevant Yeast Species

The organic acid profiles of *Lc. lactis* and eight yeast species are shown in **Figure 5**. Species-dependent differences were observed in both total acid concentration and the composition of individual acids. *Lc. lactis* produced the highest total concentration (~3.2 g/L), dominated by lactic acid (~2.0 g/L), with smaller contributions from propionic acid (~0.57 g/L), formic acid (~0.41 g/L), and acetic acid (~0.20 g/L).

Figure 5: Organic acid production profiles of *Lc. lactis* and eight food-related yeast species. The concentrations (g/L) of citric acid, lactic acid, formic acid, acetic acid, and propionic acid were determined for *Lc. lactis* and eight selected yeast species. Data represent the cumulative concentration of organic acids produced by each strain, with individual acid contributions indicated by color-coded stacked bars.

In contrast, all investigated yeast species produced substantially lower total concentrations, with none exceeding 0.5 g/L. *P. kudriazevii* showed the highest total production among the yeasts, consisting primarily of lactic acid (~0.24 g/L), acetic acid (~0.06 g/L) and propionic acid (~0.19 g/L).

Several yeast strains exhibited highly specialized acid profiles. *W. anomalus* produced almost exclusively acetic acid, whereas organic acid production in *P. membranifaciens* was dominated by propionic acid. Formic and citric acid production was undetectable across all tested species under the given conditions.

Due to analytical uncertainty associated with organic acid identification in the HPLC system, these values should be interpreted with caution (see Appendix B for chromatograms).

3.5 Effects of Organic Acids on Growth of *Bacillus* spp.

The inhibitory effects of five organic acids on *B. licheniformis* Fb2 were assessed across concentrations from 0-100 mM (**Figure 6**). All acids exhibited clear concentration-dependent inhibition, reflected by prolonged lag phases, reduced growth rates, and at higher concentrations, complete growth arrest.

A clear inhibitory threshold was observed at 50 mM and 100 mM, where all acids fully suppressed growth. At 25 mM, formic, acetic, and propionic acid caused complete inhibition, whereas lactic and citric acid still permitted growth, although with altered kinetics. At 10 mM, inhibitory effects differed between acids. Lactic, citric and formic acid had minimal impact on early growth, whereas propionic and acetic acid prolonged the lag phase. Despite delayed growth, most cultures eventually reached final OD600 values comparable to the control. Formic acid was the exception, yielding slightly lower final biomass.

Figure 6: Growth curves of *B. licheniformis* Fb2 in the presence of varying organic acids concentrations. Growth was monitored via OD600 measurements over 48 hours for formic, lactic, acetic, propionic, and citric acid. The black line represents the representative 0 mM control, as the median of the control samples. The grey shaded area shows the control range, defined as the minimum and maximum growth curves ($n=8$), one outlier was excluded from the control data. Coloured lines represent acid concentrations from 10 mM to 100 mM. Each data point represents the mean of duplicates ($n=2$).

The viability of the microbial population following exposure was quantified using \log_{10} CFU/mL (**Figure 7**) and were consistent with the inhibitory patterns observed in the growth curves. At 10 mM viability remained comparable to the control for all acids ($p>0.05$). At 25 mM, lactic acid maintained high viability, whereas citric, formic, acetic and propionic acid caused significant reductions, with propionic acid showing strongest effect. At 50-100 mM, formic, acetic, and propionic acid eliminated all detectable cells, while citric and lactic acid allowed limited survival.

Figure 7: Viable cell counts (\log_{10} CFU/mL) for *B. licheniformis* Fb2 after 48 hours incubation with different organic acids treatments. Bars represent mean \log_{10} CFU/mL for *B. licheniformis* Fb2 across concentrations (0-100 mM) of citric, lactic, formic, propionic and acetic acid. Error bars indicate SD ($n=2$), except lactic acid at 25 mM and 50 mM ($n=4$). ND= no colonies detected

Statistical analysis showed significant concentration-dependent effects on viability for all acids ($p < 0.001$), with treatments ≥ 25 mM resulting in significantly lower cell densities than the untreated control for all acids except 25 mM lactic acid.

Final pH measurements (**Figure 8**) reflected the metabolic activity of the cultures. At 10 mM, most acids allowed alkalization to near-control levels. At 25 mM lactic acid still permitted substantial alkalization, whereas the remaining acids restricted pH increases. At 50-100 mM, final pH values remained near the initial medium baseline for all acids, consistent with limited metabolic activity under strongly inhibitory conditions.

Figure 8: Impact on *Bacillus* growth in organic acid concentrations on medium pH. Bar chart displaying the pH levels of the medium following the addition of five different organic acids at concentrations of 0, 10, 25, 50 and 100 mM. The horizontal dashed line represents a representative sterile control (n=25), with the grey shaded area displaying the minimum and maximum values. Bars represent the means of duplicates (n=2). Error bars indicate standard deviation.

3.6 Effects of Nisin on Growth of *Bacillus* spp.

The antimicrobial activity of nisin against three *Bacillus* strains was assessed across concentrations from 0-50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Figure 9). The results revealed a clear dose-dependent inhibition for all three strains.

At 1-3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, growth remained robust but with slightly prolonged lag phases for *B. subtilis* var. Natto and *B. subtilis* Fb1 compared to the control. At 6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the time to reach maximum OD was markedly increased, and at $\geq 12.5 \mu\text{g/mL}$ growth was completely suppressed for all strains.

Despite these shared thresholds, strain-specific differences were evident. Both *B. subtilis* strains (var. Natto and Fb1) displayed a peak followed by a decline in OD, whereas *B. licheniformis* Fb2 showed increasing OD values over time.

Figure 9: Growth curves of three *Bacillus* strains under varying nisin concentrations. Growth curves were generated by measuring optical density (OD600) over a 48-hour period. Each panel represents a different strain (*B. subtilis* var. Natto, *B. subtilis* Fb1 and *B. licheniformis* Fb2) exposed to nisin concentrations from 0 µg/mL (control) to 50 µg/mL. Data points represent the means of triplicates (n=3).

Figure 10 demonstrates the viable cell count data for the three selected strains. Concentrations up to 6 µg/mL did not significantly reduce CFU counts for any strain (p>0.05).

Figure 10: Viable cell counts (\log_{10} CFU/mL) of selected *Bacillus* strains under varying nisin concentrations. The bar chart represents the \log_{10} CFU/mL for *B. subtilis* var. Natto, *B. subtilis* Fb1 and *B. licheniformis* Fb2 after incubation with nisin concentrations ranging from 0 to 50 µg/mL. Bars represent mean values (n=2) and error bars indicate the standard deviation. ND= No colonies detected.

At 12.5 µg/mL, *B. subtilis* var. Natto showed no detectable viability, while *B. subtilis* Fb1 and *B. licheniformis* Fb2 maintained high CFU levels comparable to the control. At 25 µg/mL and 50 µg/mL,

B. subtilis Fb1 exhibited the highest resilience, reaching $\sim 2\text{-}3 \log_{10}$ CFU/mL, whereas *B. subtilis* var. Natto and *B. licheniformis* Fb2 showed no detectable survival.

Final pH measurements (**Figure 11**) showed only minor alkalinization across concentrations. For *B. subtilis* var. Natto and *B. subtilis* Fb1, the change in pH remained stable across all nisin levels, and significant differences were not observed between concentrations ($p > 0.05$). For *B. licheniformis* Fb2, alkalinization was significantly lower at 12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ compared to the other concentrations ($p < 0.05$), consistent with reduced metabolic activity under inhibitory conditions.

Figure 11: Impact of nisin induced growth inhibition of *Bacillus* on pH of medium. The final pH of the culture medium (BHI) was measured following 48-hour incubation for *B. subtilis* var. Natto, *B. subtilis* Fb1 and *B. licheniformis* Fb2 across different nisin concentrations. The dashed line represents the pH of the sterile control ($\text{pH } 7.15 \pm 0.09$). Bars represent the means of duplicates ($n=2$) and error bars indicate standard deviations.

3.7 Growth and Inhibition of *Bacillus* spp. in Plant Matrix

Based on the findings in the screening assay, *W. anomalus*, *K. marxianus* and *Lc. lactis* were selected for co-culture experiment with *B. licheniformis*. The effect of co-cultivation on *B. licheniformis* Fb2 was evaluated at three initial inoculation levels (2,3 and 4 \log_{10} CFU/g) to determine how interspecies interactions influence final cell densities (**Figure 12**).

Figure 12: Growth of *Bacillus licheniformis* Fb2 in monoculture and co-culture systems. The bar chart illustrates the cell densities (\log_{10} CFU/g) of *B. licheniformis* Fb2 following 24-hour cultivation at three initial inoculation levels (2,3, and 4 \log_{10} CFU/g). Comparisons are made between *B. licheniformis* Fb2 in monoculture (blue) and in co-culture with *W. anomalous* (orange), *K. marxianus* (green) and *Lc. lactis* (red). The horizontal line at 6 \log_{10} CFU/g indicates the limit of detection (LOD), samples falling below this threshold are marked as <LOD. Data points represent the mean of duplicates (n=2), except for *B. licheniformis* + *W. anomalous* at 2 log (n=1) and *B. licheniformis* + *W. anomalous* at 3 log (n=3), *B. licheniformis* + *K. marxianus* at 2 log (n=3) and all co-cultures with *Lc. lactis* (n=3). Error bars indicate the standard deviation.

In monoculture, *B. licheniformis* Fb2 did not grow at the lowest inoculation level and remained below the detection limit. At higher inoculations levels, monocultures reached 6.9-7.3 \log_{10} CFU/g after 24 hours. Contamination was detected in monoculture samples and is noted as potential limitation.

Co-cultivation with *Lc. lactis* resulted in complete suppression of *B. licheniformis* Fb2 at all inoculation levels, with cell densities remaining below the detection limit. In contrast, co-cultivation with the yeast species *W. anomalous* and *K. marxianus* demonstrated an increase in cell densities for *B. licheniformis* Fb2 across all inoculation levels. When co-cultured with *W. anomalous*, cell densities reached between 7.2 - 8.3 \log_{10} CFU/g, and with *K. marxianus* cell densities reached between 6.5 and 8.2 \log_{10} CFU/g.

4. Discussion

The present study investigated the bioprotective potential of *Lactococcus lactis* and selected food-relevant yeast species against *Bacillus* spp. in both in vitro and plant-based systems and explored which underlying mechanisms may have contributed to the observed inhibition. Overall, the results demonstrated clear species- and strain-dependent differences in inhibitory activity and susceptibility, which cannot not be fully explained by acidification or organic acid production alone, and likely involves additional mechanisms.

The investigated lactic acid bacteria and yeast species displayed clear differences in inhibitory activity in the spot assay, based on measured inhibition zones. Only *Lc. lactis*, *Wickerhamomyces anomalus* and *Kluyveromyces marxianus* produced clear and reproducible inhibition zones across replicates, whereas the remaining species showed no or minimal antagonistic activity. Some variability between replicates was observed, which may reflect differences in initial physiological state of the spotted cultures, or minor variations in inoculum cell density.

The inhibitory activity of *Lc. lactis* against *Bacillus subtilis* in the present study was strain-dependent, as inhibition was observed for *B. subtilis* var. Natto, whereas no inhibitory effect was detected against *B. subtilis* Fb1 and Fb4. This is consistent with previous studies that have reported inhibition of *B. subtilis* by *Lc. lactis* (Pokorski & Trzaskowska, 2023; Sadiq et al., 2014) whereas Hladíková et al. (2012), similar to the present study, found no inhibitory effect against *B. subtilis*. This indicates variability in susceptibility of *B. subtilis* strains to *Lc. lactis*.

The antagonistic activity of *W. anomalus* and *K. marxianus* is consistent with previous studies, where inhibitory effects against *B. subtilis* have been reported to some degree (Meneghin et al., 2010; Novichenko et al., 2024; Rogalska et al., 2025). In contrast, *S. cerevisiae* and the majority of the investigated yeast species showed no detectable inhibition, which is consistent with reports that many strains lack antagonistic activity against *B. subtilis* (Meneghin et al., 2010; Novichenko et al., 2024). However, inhibition is known to be strain dependent, and Lima et al. (2017) have demonstrated that some strains of *S. cerevisiae* (25%) are capable of inhibiting *B. subtilis*, and the strain used in the present study therefore likely belongs to the non-inhibitory majority. Overall, the differences in inhibitory activity suggest antimicrobial effects in yeast are not universal but depend on species-specific metabolite production or competitive interactions.

To the best of my knowledge, no studies have investigated the inhibitory activity of *Lc. lactis* or the selected yeast species against *B. subtilis* var. Natto or *Bacillus licheniformis*. These may exhibit

different susceptibility profiles compared to the *B. subtilis* strains investigated in previous studies. As demonstrated in the present study, *B. subtilis* var. Natto and the two strains of *B. licheniformis* (Fb2 and Fb3) showed higher susceptibility to inhibitory activity compared to the *B. subtilis* strains (Fb1 and Fb4). This suggests that species- and strain-level differences within the *Bacillus* genus may influence overall sensitivity to bioprotective cultures.

The inhibitory patterns observed in the screening assay led to further investigation of *Bacillus* growth across a defined pH range to assess the contribution of acidification to overall inhibition.

Across all strains, low pH (3.5-4.0) resulted in complete growth arrest and for some strains (Natto and Fb2), loss of detectable viability at pH 3.5. At pH 4.0 all strains maintained low but detectable populations. These findings were further supported by de-acidification data, where minimal alkalization at pH 3.5-4.0 indicated strongly reduced metabolic activity across all strains. Overall, this confirms that pH values below 4.0 exceed the tolerance range of the tested *Bacillus* strains.

At pH ≥ 4.2 , species-dependent recovery was observed. *B. subtilis* (Fb1 and Fb4) showed earlier metabolic recovery than *B. licheniformis* (Fb2 and Fb3), consistent with previous observations that *B. subtilis* may exhibit higher acid resilience (Rodriguez et al., 1992). This also provides important context for the inhibitory effects observed in the screening assays, as strains showing reduced susceptibility in the spot assay (*B. subtilis* Fb1 and Fb4) may reflect higher acid tolerance.

At pH 4.4 growth increased for several strains. *B. licheniformis* Fb2 adapted after a prolonged lag phase, whereas Fb3 showed no detectable growth. However, CFU counts confirmed the presence of viable cells across all strains, suggesting growth inhibition at this pH is predominantly bacteriostatic, rather than bactericidal. The high variability observed for *B. subtilis* var. Natto and *B. licheniformis* Fb3 likely reflects growth occurring near the lower permissive pH limit, where adaption is heterogeneous rather than synchronized across the population.

Once the pH threshold for growth was surpassed (≥ 4.4), most strains reached high final OD and CFU values, and differences between pH 4.8 and 7.0 were minimal. This indicates that *Bacillus* growth is highly sensitive near its lower pH boundary, but less affected within the permissive growth range. These findings are consistent with previous work on *Bacillus* spp. acid tolerance. A study by Rodriguez et al. (1992), investigating growth of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* in tomato juice, reported that two out of five strains were able to grow at pH 4.4, whereas no growth occurred at pH 4.0 or 4.2 for any strains. However, the present findings for *B. subtilis* var. Natto differ from Chen et al. (2022) who reported survival at pH 3.0, suggesting strain-specific variation in acid tolerance.

These findings highlight that acidification may contribute to the inhibitory effects observed in the screening assays, however, its relevance depends on the acidification capacity of *Lc. lactis* and yeast species. *W. anomalus* reached pH values (4.23) within the inhibitory range for growth suppression of *B. licheniformis* (Fb2 and Fb3) in the present study, suggesting acidification could contribute to the observed inhibition. Controlled pH experiments would be needed to confirm whether acidification is a primary factor for the observed inhibition, as previously applied in studies investigating acidification-dependent inhibition (Tejero-Sariñena et al., 2012). In contrast, *K. marxianus* and *Lc. lactis* only reached permissive pH values (4.84 and 5.36, respectively) for *Bacillus* growth, suggesting that their inhibitory effects are unlikely to be driven solely by pH reduction and may involve additional antimicrobial mechanisms, such as organic acid production or bacteriocin activity.

Since acidification alone does not fully explain the inhibitory patterns observed in the screening assays, additional metabolic factors must be considered, such as organic acids. In the present study, increasing concentrations of organic acids resulted in a clear, concentration-dependent inhibition of *B. licheniformis* Fb2, with complete growth arrest observed at 50-100 mM for all acids tested, however with viable cell counts at lactic and citric acid. At lower concentrations, clear differences in antimicrobial potency were observed, with formic, acetic and propionic acid showing stronger inhibitory effects compared to lactic and citric acid. These differences are consistent with previous studies showing that acids with higher proportions of undissociated molecules at a given pH exhibit stronger antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus* spp. (Antone et al., 2023; Rosenquist & Hansen, 1998; Yang et al., 2015). Therefore, due to the differences in pKa values between acids, it is important to know the pH of a product, to achieve maximum inhibitory effect.

Interestingly, formic acid caused complete growth inhibition at 25 mM and no detectable viability at 50-100 mM, despite its lower pKa value compared to lactic acid. This agrees with earlier findings suggesting that molecular size contributes to antimicrobial potency, enabling a more rapid diffusion of formic acid across the membrane (Antone et al., 2023).

The complexity of organic acid inhibition is also reflected in reported MIC values for *Bacillus* spp., which vary substantially across studies, ranging from 1.75-23 mM for acetic acid and 3.6-34 mM for propionic acid (Ajingi et al., 2022; Antone et al., 2023; Hsiao & Siebert, 1999), which likely reflects differences in pH, medium composition and inoculum size, in addition to strain-specific variation.

The inhibitory thresholds established in the present study provide a basis for evaluating whether organic acid production by *Lc. lactis* and yeast species is sufficient to explain observed inhibition in the screening assays. The organic acid profiles revealed clear species-dependent differences in both total acid production and composition, demonstrating different metabolic profiles among the investigated microorganisms. *Lc. lactis* produced the highest total concentration of organic acids (3.22 g/L), dominated by lactic acid (2 g/L \approx 22.2 mM), with smaller amounts of propionic (0.6 g/L \approx 8.1 mM), formic acid (0.41 g/L \approx 8.9 mM), and acetic acid (0.2 g/L \approx 3.3 mM). The detected organic acids are broadly consistent with those reported by Özcelik et al. (2016) who demonstrated production of lactic, acetic and propionic acid by *Lc. lactis*, although at lower concentrations for lactic and acetic acid than observed here (0.5 g/L, 0.35 g/L, 1.15 g/L, respectively), and with no detection of formic acid. These quantitative differences could be due to medium composition and growth conditions, however lactic acid generally remains the dominant metabolite across environments (Özcelik et al., 2016). Lactic acid is among the least potent organic acids in the present study, with limited inhibition observed at corresponding concentrations to those quantified by HPLC of *Lc. lactis*. Although minor amounts of more inhibitory acids such as propionic, formic and acetic acid were detected, their concentrations remained below inhibitory thresholds of *Bacillus* spp. This suggests that organic acid production alone is insufficient to explain the inhibitory activity of *Lc. lactis*.

In contrast, all yeast species produced substantially lower total organic acid concentrations, with none exceeding 0.5 g/L. This suggests that organic acid production alone is unlikely to explain the inhibitory activity observed in the screening assay for *W. anomalus* and *K. marxianus*, indicating that additional antimicrobial mechanisms may contribute. Several studies have reported similar organic acids and amounts to those found in the present study, and generally fall below thresholds for inhibition of *Bacillus* spp. *S. cerevisiae* has previously shown to produce organic acids including acetic, succinic, citric and malic acid during fermentation, with acetic and citric acid typically present in lower amounts, consistent with the present findings (Liu et al., 2021). Considerable strain-dependent variation in organic acid production has also been reported for *W. anomalus*. García-Fraile et al. (2013) observed acetic acid concentrations ranging from non-detectable levels to 1.48 g/L, while citric acid production ranged from non-detectable to 0.91 g/L. The concentrations observed in the present study fall within this reported range and highlights the influence of strain variation on yeast metabolism. For *K. marxianus*, previous studies have reported production of lactic acid (3.01 g/L), together with smaller amounts of acetic acid (0.007 g/L), while citric acid remained undetected in

fermented rice soup after 24 hours (Liu et al., 2023). The higher lactic acid production reported in the literature compared to the present study indicates strong medium-dependent variation in organic acid production.

To the best of my knowledge, published data describing organic acid production remain limited for several of the remaining yeast species, restricting direct comparisons with the present findings.

Despite the analytical limitations of the HPLC method, all quantified organic acids peaks were well below the minimum inhibitory concentrations determined in this study, this strongly suggests that organic acids alone cannot account for the inhibitory effects observed.

Since organic acid production and pH reduction alone could not fully account for the inhibitory effects observed in the screening assays for *Lc. lactis*, the potential role of bacteriocin-mediated inhibition was further investigated using nisin.

Nisin is approved for use in a wide range of foods, with permitted levels ranging from 3-25 mg/kg depending on food product (EFSA, 2017). The concentrations tested in the present study (1-50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, equivalent to 1-50 mg/L) therefore overlap with levels relevant to food systems, increasing the practical relevance of the findings. However, it should be noted that these results were obtained under laboratory conditions and may not directly translate to complex food matrices. For example, a study by Rosenquist and Hansen (1998), demonstrated that nisin often performs poorly in real food systems despite strong activity in broth, even at concentrations exceeding those used in the present study. They propose that the reduced efficacy could be due to nisin binding to food particles, uneven distribution, poor solubility, and degradation by nisinase enzymes produced by some *Bacillus* strains.

The findings in the present study demonstrated that nisin effectively suppressed growth, although bactericidal activity varied between strains and concentrations. At $\geq 12.5 \mu\text{g/mL}$, growth was completely suppressed for all strains, while viability differed significantly between species. *B. subtilis* var. Natto showed complete loss of viability at 12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, whereas *B. subtilis* Fb1 and *B. licheniformis* Fb2 maintained high viable counts. Furthermore, *B. subtilis* Fb1 demonstrates extra robustness against nisin as it had viable counts even at 25-50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. This indicates that nisin sensitivity is strongly strain-dependent, even within the related *Bacillus* species. For *B. subtilis* var. Natto and *B. licheniformis* Fb2, inhibitory concentrations fell within the range used in foods, suggesting nisin could be capable of inhibiting *Bacillus* spp. at levels that are legally permitted.

The reported inhibitory concentrations for *B. subtilis* range from 16 to 156.3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Ajingi et al., 2022; Sani et al., 2022; Tong et al., 2025) and in some cases up to 900 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Alnemr et al., 2015), highlighting variability in nisin efficacy depending on strain and experimental conditions. To the best of my knowledge, published data for the inhibition of *B. licheniformis* and *B. subtilis* var. *Natto* by nisin remain limited.

In the screening assay, *Lc. lactis* inhibited *B. subtilis* var. *Natto* and the two *B. licheniformis* strains (Fb2 and Fb3), while limited inhibition was observed for *B. subtilis* (Fb1 and Fb4). This may reflect higher resistance of these strains to bacteriocin-mediated inhibition, consistent with the lower susceptibility towards nisin found in this study.

Although nisin production by the *Lc. lactis* strain used in this study was not quantified, reported production levels in plant food fermentations can reach concentrations overlapping with inhibitory ranges observed here (Siroli et al., 2019), suggesting that bacteriocin production may contribute to the inhibitory effects of *Lc. lactis* observed in the screening assay.

Although pH reduction and organic acid production by *Lc. lactis* were insufficient to inhibit *Bacillus* spp. when acting alone, they may still contribute to the overall antimicrobial effect when combined with other inhibitory compounds, such as nisin. The combination of nisin and organic acids has previously been shown to exhibit synergistic activity against *B. subtilis*. For example, one study reported synergistic effects using organic acids such as acetic and propionic acid in combination with nisin for control of *B. subtilis* (Ajingi et al., 2022). A second study by the same authors, demonstrated reduced MIC values when nisin was combined with organic acids such as formic, lactic and citric acid (Ajingi et al., 2020). This supports the possibility of potential synergistic interactions in the present study.

It should be mentioned that some experiments were performed in duplicate (elaborated in Methods), which limits statistical power and may contribute to experimental variability. Therefore, observed trends should be interpreted cautiously and preferably be confirmed in future studies with larger biological replication.

The primary aim of the co-culture experiment on solid-state fermentation of fava beans, was to evaluate whether *Lc. lactis* or selected yeast species could inhibit the growth of *B. licheniformis* Fb2 in a plant-based food matrix. However, interpretation is limited by contamination of the monoculture

controls, which prevents quantitative comparison. Therefore, the results are interpreted qualitatively and can be used as a preliminary experiment.

In co-cultures with *W. anomalus* and *K. marxianus*, *B. licheniformis* remained detectable across conditions, indicating that these yeasts did not exert a strong inhibitory effect under the tested conditions. The limited inhibitory effect in the plant-based food matrix compared to the screening assay results could be due to several factors. Nutrient competition with *Bacillus* spp. may have played a role, or the activity of antimicrobial compounds, such as peptides or killer toxins, could have been reduced in the complex food matrix, similar to the observed reduction in nisin efficacy in real food systems (Rosenquist & Hansen, 1998)

To the best of my knowledge, no studies have investigated yeast inhibition of spoilage bacteria in plant-based matrices. However, yeasts can inhibit filamentous fungi in plant foods such as tomatoes (Lanhuang et al., 2022), supporting their ability to produce antimicrobial compounds, or use other inhibitory mechanisms, in plant matrices. However, these antifungal effects, cannot be directly compared to interactions with *Bacillus* spp.

Together, this finding suggests that antibacterial activity of yeasts in plant-based foods cannot be assumed from in vitro screening alone and requires validation within relevant food matrices. The inhibitory potential of yeasts against bacteria in plant-based foods remains largely unexplored.

In contrast, *B. licheniformis* was not detected in any co-cultures with *Lc. lactis*, suggesting a strong inhibitory interaction under the tested conditions. This observation is supported by the fact that, despite the compromised monoculture controls, higher bacterial counts were still detected in control samples than in the *Lc. lactis* co-cultures, indicating a reduction of *Bacillus* viability in the presence of *Lc. lactis*. Furthermore, *Lc. lactis* demonstrated the strongest inhibition in the screening assay (12.67 ± 2.31 mm zone against *B. licheniformis* Fb2), confirming the inhibition also observed in the plant-based food matrix. This finding is consistent with previous studies. Pokorski and Trzaskowska (2023) reported a 2-4 log reduction of *B. Subtilis* during co-fermentation of barley products with *Lc. lactis*, which they attributed to organic acid production and potential bacteriocin-like inhibitory substances activity. However, these mechanisms were not directly quantified, and the study therefore does not provide conclusive evidence for the specific inhibitory mechanisms. Similarly, Kato et al. (1999) found *Lc. lactis* completely inhibited *B. subtilis* in fermented soybeans. In their study, only a slight decrease in pH was observed, suggesting that acidification alone could not explain the inhibition. Instead, they demonstrated high nisin production in cooked soybean, indicating that

bacteriocin activity was the likely mechanism. Together, these studies support the conclusion that *Lc. lactis* can inhibit *Bacillus* spp. in plant-based systems, potentially through a combination of acidification and bacteriocin production. Although the present study did not quantify bacteriocin production, it may have contributed to the observed inhibitory effect.

Based on the combined results of this study, it is not possible to identify a single dominant mechanism responsible for inhibition. However, the data indicate that acidification and organic acid production alone are insufficient in most cases, which opens the possibility that additional factors, such as bacteriocin activity by *Lc. lactis*, killer toxins or antimicrobial peptides by yeasts, or synergistic interactions, may have contributed to the observed inhibitions. These interpretations remain uncertain, as the present study did not directly quantify these mechanisms, but they align with patterns reported in previous literature. In the case of *W. anomalus*, acidification may represent the primary inhibitory mechanism for some *Bacillus* spp., as it reached low pH levels (4.23), which corresponds to the threshold at which growth inhibition of *Bacillus licheniformis* was observed.

The differences observed between in vitro assays and the plant-based matrix further highlight environmental complexity. These differences observed in inhibition patterns for yeasts underline the importance of evaluating bioprotective cultures in food-relevant systems, where their activity may differ from simplified laboratory settings. While the present study cannot fully resolve the mechanisms behind these interactions, the results provide a foundation for future work aimed at investigating how different factors affect microbial inhibition in plant-based foods.

5. Conclusion

This study investigated the inhibitory potential of *Lactococcus lactis* and selected food-related yeast species against *Bacillus* spp. and evaluated the contribution of pH, organic acids and nisin sensitivity to inhibition. The findings revealed clear species- and strain-dependent differences in both antagonistic activity and *Bacillus* susceptibility. Among the investigated microorganisms, *Wickerhamomyces anomalus*, *Kluyveromyces marxianus* and *Lc. lactis* showed the strongest inhibitory activity in the screening assays, while *Bacillus subtilis* var. Natto and *Bacillus licheniformis* (Fb2 and Fb3) were the most susceptible *Bacillus* strains.

Growth of *Bacillus* spp. was strongly reduced at $\text{pH} \leq 4.2$, and propionic, acetic and formic acid showed the strongest inhibitory effects at ≥ 50 mM. However, measured organic acid concentrations produced by *Lc. lactis* and the yeasts remained below inhibitory thresholds, indicating that organic acids alone could not explain the observed inhibition. *W. anomalus* showed the strongest acidification of $\text{pH} 4.23$, reaching growth inhibitory values of *B. licheniformis*. However, if pH reduction was the primary inhibitory factor, remains unknown.

Nisin levels of ≥ 12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ caused complete growth inhibition, however with strain-dependent survival detected. While nisin production by the *Lc. lactis* strain was not quantified, the inhibition observed suggests that bacteriocin activity likely contributed.

In the plant-based matrix, *Lc. lactis* suppressed *B. licheniformis*, whereas the tested yeast species showed limited inhibitory effects, although due to compromised controls, these findings should be interpreted cautiously.

Overall, inhibition observed in this study cannot be fully explained by the mechanisms investigated, indicating that additional or synergistic factors may be involved, but this remains unsolved. The findings support the potential of *Lc. lactis* as a bioprotective culture in plant-based food systems, while the role of yeasts remains less clear and requires further clarification.

6. Perspectives

The findings of this study contribute to understanding microbial interactions in plant-based food matrices but also highlight the complexity of these interactions. Although the present study identified clear inhibitory patterns *in vitro*, the underlying antimicrobial mechanisms remain only partly resolved. Future studies should therefore focus on identification and quantification of undefined inhibitory compounds, including bacteriocins produced by *Lc. lactis* and potential antimicrobial metabolites or killer toxins potentially produced by yeast species.

To assess the genetic potential for nisin production in *Lc. lactis*, PCR-based screening using primers targeting nisin biosynthesis genes can be applied. Such approaches, as previously demonstrated by Kruger et al. (2013), can allow detection of genes encoding bacteriocins. In yeasts, killer toxin production may similarly be investigated using PCR-based detection of killer toxin associated genes, or dsRNA elements linked to killer activity (Quintero-Blanco et al., 2022). However, the presence of these genes does not necessarily reflect expression. Therefore, functional assays should be combined with identification and quantification methods of these secreted antimicrobial compounds to confirm actual production and antimicrobial activity.

To determine whether inhibition is caused by proteinaceous compounds such as bacteriocins, killer toxins or antimicrobial peptides, cell-free supernatants could be subjected to protease sensitivity assays using enzymes such as Proteinase K or pepsin, followed by inhibition testing. Loss of antimicrobial activity after protease treatment would indicate a protein- or peptide-based inhibitor (Furtado et al., 2014). Furthermore, neutralisation of the supernatant would help determine whether inhibition is caused by acidification and organic acids (Tejero-Sariñena et al., 2012).

For compound-level identification, LC-MS/MS-based approaches could be used for detecting and characterizing antimicrobial peptides and metabolites, including nisin or yeast-derived compounds (Branco et al., 2014; Nandakumar & Talapatra, 2014). This method provides molecular mass and fragmentation patterns supporting compound identification. Where standards are available, targeted LC-MS/MS can further be applied for quantitative analysis of known antimicrobial compounds.

As yeast-mediated inhibition may also involve volatile organic compounds (VOCs), GS-MS analysis can be used to characterize inhibitory VOCs profiles as described by Contarino et al. (2019).

Overall, these methods would provide a more detailed understanding of the antimicrobial mechanisms and support development of targeted bioprotective cultures for plant-based food systems.

The inconsistency between screening assays and the plant-matrix experiment further highlights the importance of validating antimicrobial activity under realistic food conditions. Future work should therefore include controlled plant-based fermentation systems with improved contamination control to better understand microbial interactions, and whether inhibition observed *in vitro*, is possible in a complex food matrix. This is important for the application of efficient bioprotective cultures.

7. References

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Appendix

Appendix A - Screening assay: Inhibition zones

D. hansenii (MD 02)

K. lactis (SP19#10)

K. marxianus (TSL3)

P. kudriazevii (36h3c2)

P. membranefaciens (PM6-21)

S. cerevisiae (18-28)

S. occidentalis (DSM3794)

W. anomalus (SP17#2)

Lc. Lactis (NcimB702091)

Appendix B - HPLC Calibration and Chromatograms

Table B1 presents the calibration data for the organic acids analysed by HPLC, including the concentration range, linear regression equations and coefficients of determination (R^2)

Table B1: Concentration range, regression equations, and R^2 for organic acid calibration curves.

Organic acid	Range (g/L)	Regression	R^2
Citric acid	0.5-2.0	$y = 2E-06x - 0.4461$	0.954
Lactic acid	0.5-2.0	$y = 0.0000043x - 0.0213$	0.999
Formic acid	0.5-2.0	$y = 0.0000179x - 0.00324$	0.999
Acetic acid	0.5-2.0	$y = 0.0000049x + 0.00119$	0.999
Propionic acid	0.5-2.0	$y = 0.0000171x - 0.01607$	0.999

Figure B1-B12 illustrates HPLC chromatograms, both from standards and samples with identified organic acids indicated. Citric acid was excluded from further interpretation, as the observed peaks may represent overlapping compounds and the standard mixture did not fully correspond to the sample chromatograms. In the *Lc. lactis* sample, the predominant peak is most likely lactic acid, resulting in an approximate retention time shift of one minute across the chromatograms. Due to uncertainties in peak identification and retention time, the results were interpreted with caution.

Figure B1: HPLC chromatogram of a 0.5 g/L standard mixture with identified peaks

Figure B2: HPLC chromatogram of a 1.0 g/L standard mixture with identified peaks

Figure B3: HPLC chromatogram of a 2.0 g/L standard mixture with identified peaks

Lc. lactis

Figure B4: HPLC chromatogram of *Lc. lactis* and identified organic acids. A retention time shift of approximately one minute was observed compared to the standards.

D. hansenii

Figure B5: HPLC chromatogram of *D. hansenii* and identified organic acids. A retention time shift of approximately one minute was observed compared to the standards.

K. lactis

Figure B6: HPLC chromatogram of *K. lactis* and identified organic acids. A retention time shift of approximately one minute was observed compared to the standards.

K. marxianus

Figure B7: HPLC chromatogram of *K. marxianus* and identified organic acids. A retention time shift of approximately one minute was observed compared to the standards.

P. kudriazevii

Figure B8: HPLC chromatogram of *P. kudriazevii* and identified organic acids. A retention time shift of approximately one minute was observed compared to the standards.

P. membranifaciens

Figure B9: HPLC chromatogram of *P. membranifaciens* and identified organic acids. A retention time shift of approximately one minute was observed compared to the standards.

S. cerevisiae

Figure B10: HPLC chromatogram of *S. cerevisiae* and identified organic acids. A retention time shift of approximately one minute was observed compared to the standards.

S. occidentalis

Figure B11: HPLC chromatogram of *S. occidentalis* and identified organic acids. A retention time shift of approximately one minute was observed compared to the standards.

W. anomalus

Figure B12: HPLC chromatogram of *W. anomalus* and identified organic acids. A retention time shift of approximately one minute was observed compared to the standards.

Table B2 shows the concentration (g/L) of organic acids quantified by HPLC in each sample.

Table B2: Organic acid quantification (g/L) of individual acids for each sample, calculated from the standard regression equations.

Sample	g/L				
	Citric Acid	Lactic Acid	Formic Acid	Acetic Acid	Propionic Acid
<i>Lc. Lactis</i>		2.028313	0.4120267	0.207274	0.573463
<i>D. hansenii</i>		0.070354		0.042299	0.268179
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>		0.115493		0.03291	
<i>K. lactis</i>		0.102392		0.05829	0.225168
<i>P. Kudriazevii</i>		0.244909		0.056321	0.190223
<i>K. marxianus</i>		0.040751		0.03673	0.189699
<i>W. anomalus</i>		0.009829		0.086971	
<i>P. membranifaciens</i>					0.178383
<i>S. occidentalis</i>		0.145639		0.041845	0.165267

Appendix C - Statistical Analysis

The results of ANOVA analyses for the experiments are presented in tables C1-C7. Due to the large number of pairwise comparisons, full Tukey HSD post-hoc results are not reported. Instead, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) are summarized using letters (a, b, c, ...) in Tables 4 and 5.

Table C1: Two-way ANOVA - pH- monitoring of *Lc. lactis* and food-relevant yeast species (Data from table 4)

	sum_sq	df	F	p
C(species)	8.828415	8.0	19.419359	1.146010e-16
C(time)	33.814314	4.0	148.758828	8.646554e-39
(Cspecies):C(time)	6.569593	32.0	3.612689	8.964456e-07
Residual	5.114467	90.0	NaN	NaN

Tabel C2: One-way ANOVA - De-acidifying potential of five *Bacillus* strains across an initial pH gradient (Data from table 5)

		sum_sq	df	F	p
<i>B. subtilis</i> var. Natto	C(start_pH)	6.844144	7.0	3.186296	0.063325
	Residual	2.454850	8.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. subtilis</i> Fb1	C(start_pH)	9.923644	7.0	15.956816	0.000408
	Residual	0.710750	8.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb2	C(start_pH)	9.5700	7.0	12.873285	0.000876
	Residual	0.8496	8.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb3	C(start_pH)	9.889194	7.0	6.545965	0.008357
	Residual	1.726550	8.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. Subtilis</i> Fb4	C(start_pH)	8.81696	7.0	14.11617	0.001216
	Residual	0.62460	7.0	NaN	NaN

Tabel C3: One-way ANOVA - log₁₀ CFU across pH gradient

		sum_sq	df	F	p
<i>B. subtilis</i> var. Natto	C(start_pH)	123.264779	4.0	2.88352	0.137993
	Residual	53.435029	5.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. subtilis</i> Fb1	C(start_pH)	51.739160	4.0	86.416876	0.00039
	Residual	0.598716	4.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb2	C(start_pH)	166.841936	4.0	20.750169	0.002584
	Residual	10.050637	5.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb3	C(start_pH)	152.837223	4.0	10.603407	0.011688
	Residual	18.017467	5.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. Subtilis</i> Fb4	C(start_pH)	94.282190	4.0	14.763597	0.011562
	Residual	6.386126	4.0	NaN	NaN

Tabel C4: One-way ANOVA - De-acidifying potential across organic acids

		sum_sq	df	F	p
Citric Acid	C(conc)	1.198458	4.0	17.696791	5.225226e-07
	Residual	0.423261	25.0	NaN	NaN
Lactic Acid	C(conc)	2.157569	4.0	86.149775	3.018967e-14
	Residual	0.156527	25.0	NaN	NaN
Formic Acid	C(conc)	1.107871	4.0	31.020702	2.309176e-09
	Residual	0.223212	25.0	NaN	NaN
Propionic Acid	C(conc)	1.319061	4.0	53.949136	6.166816e-12
	Residual	0.152813	25.0	NaN	NaN
Actetic Acid	C(conc)	1.923172	4.0	21.191623	9.904936e-08
	Residual	0.567197	25.0	NaN	NaN

Tabel C5: One-way ANOVA - log₁₀ CFU across Organic acids

		sum_sq	df	F	p
Citric Acid	C(conc)	141.241297	4.0	1524.9232	6.715515e-08
	Residual	0.033806	5.0	NaN	NaN
Lactic Acid	C(conc)	89.575406	4.0	1041.5073	5.504520e-12
	Residual	0.193512	9.0	NaN	NaN
Formic Acid	C(conc)	14.560300	2.0	17215.237	8.132248e-07
	Residual	0.001269	3.0	NaN	NaN
Propionic Acid	C(conc)	19.953139	2.0	454.78200	0.000188
	Residual	0.065811	3.0	NaN	NaN
Actetic Acid	C(conc)	14.441020	2.0	39596.871	2.331422e-07
	Residual	0.000547	3.0	NaN	NaN

Tabel C6: One-way ANOVA - De-acidifying potential across Nisin nisin concentrations

		sum_sq	df	F	p
<i>B. subtilis</i> var. Natto	C(conc)	0.732009	6.0	3.313204	0.030345
	Residual	0.515519	14.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. subtilis</i> Fb1	C(conc)	0.058016	6.0	1.95388	0.200624
	Residual	0.034641	7.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb2	C(conc)	0.488459	6.0	13.082985	0.001704
	Residual	0.043558	7.0	NaN	NaN

Tabel C7: One-way ANOVA - log₁₀ CFU across nisin concentrations

		sum_sq	df	F	p
<i>B. subtilis</i> var. Natto	C(conc)	30.714945	4.0	256.5574	1.652343e-11
	Residual	0.359159	12.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. subtilis</i> Fb1	C(conc)	153.999136	6.0	252.9263	6.201230e-15
	Residual	1.623652	16.0	NaN	NaN
<i>B. licheniformis</i> Fb2	C(conc)	1.151492	4.0	18.455038	0.000028
	Residual	0.202782	13.0	NaN	NaN

Declaration of using generative AI tools

I/we have used generative AI as an aid/tool (please tick)

I/we have **NOT** used generative AI as an aid/tool (please tick)

List which GAI tools you have used and include the link to the platform (if possible):

<https://copilot.microsoft.com>

<https://notebooklm.google.com>

<https://chatgpt.com>

Describe how generative AI has been used in the exam paper:

1) Purpose (what did you use the tool for?)

I used Co-pilot for idea development and for sparring regarding the overall structure of the project, including what might be relevant to include or exclude based on my own initial ideas. Furthermore, did I use it for literature searching. Lastly, did I use it to assist with coding in Pycharm in relation to figures and statistical analyses, both to identify specific codes I could use and to detects errors in my codes. No data were uploaded into the AI system, only raw code fragments were generated or reviewed.

Moreover, did I use Notebooklm to elaborate on and explain complex literature to gain more clear understanding of theoretical concepts and materials.

I used ChatGPT for generating the title page illustration.

2) Work phase (when in the process did you use GAI?)

I used AI in the initial phase for idea generation and structural planning, and then throughout the process for literature searching and for sparring regarding the interpretation of identified literature, and also for help with coding.

3) What did you do with the output? (including any editing of or continued work on the output)

I used outputs as inspiration and as points for reflection that I subsequently developed further myself.